

How can ISO 13482:2014 account for the ethical and social considerations of robotic exoskeletons?

Eduard Fosch-Villaronga ^{a,*}, Carlos José Calleja ^a, Hadassah Drukarch ^a, Diego Torricelli ^b

^a eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies, Leiden University, the Netherlands

^b Spanish Research Council (CSIC), Spain

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes and classifies regulatory gaps and inconsistencies in ISO 13482:2014 ('Safety Requirements for Personal Care Robots'), specifically regarding robotic lower-limb exoskeletons, being personal care robots, for everyday activities. Following a systematic literature review, our findings support the conclusion that, even though ISO 13482:2014 has proven to be a substantial step towards regulating that type of wearable robot, it fails to address safety sufficiently and comprehensively. That failure results in a general overlook of critical legal, ethical, and social considerations when designing robots, with the consequence that seemingly safe systems might nonetheless harm end-users. Notwithstanding those limitations and impediments to the development of safe technologies, to date, there has been no thorough assessment of how the standard regulates the development of exoskeletons and whether it requires any improvement in light of ethical, legal, and societal considerations. To bridge this gap, we compile relevant areas for improvement concerning ISO 13482:2014 fueled by these considerations. We do so in an accessible manner and provide concrete recommendations to help decision-makers overcome the standard's drawbacks.

1. Introduction

Wearable robots, and particularly exoskeletons to support the lower limbs, are emerging technologies that promise to return mobility to individuals or make physical work more comfortable and safer in the industry. These devices are developed to amplify human strength and agility, thereby supporting the movement of the limbs to help individuals who have lost the ability to move them by themselves [1]. These robots are intimately intertwined with the human body. This connection profoundly impacts how users experience their environment and how others experience them [2].

Despite their great promise and significance, exoskeleton technologies raise several legal, ethical, and social concerns that confront legal scholars, ethicists, the industry, and society [3]. The European project Cost Action 16116 on Wearable Robots recently covered some questions. For instance, will exoskeletons protect employees' health or give rise to detrimental expectations? If we focus on restoring people's ability to walk, will we disregard those who cannot? Will wearable robots be a technology for the masses, or will they remain a luxury for just a few?

Who will be liable if using the robot results in harm or injury? The human who controls it or the robot that has done it? [2,4,5].

While some of these questions arise due to traditionally siloed disciplines, the absence of technical standards capable of tackling those issues also contributes to it. A recurrent barrier encountered by developers [6], researchers [7,8], and policymakers [9] is that current regulations do not frame personal care robots adequately. On the contrary, rules for robots used in care applications remain scattered and cover issues unevenly [7,10,11]. For instance, ISO 13482:2014 does not account for gender and sex considerations and thus fails to guide developers in making robots fit for different categories of people [12,13]. ISO 13482:2014 also focuses, for the most part, on physical safety, even though interacting with most wearable robots brings to the table a broader array of issues like the security of networks, trust, and cognitive problems [14–16].

Seeing that failing to acknowledge and address those concerns may be potentially irreversible [17], this paper analyzes and classifies regulatory gaps and inconsistencies found in ISO 13482:2014 ('Safety Requirements for Personal Care Robots'). Notwithstanding the growing

* Corresponding author. eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies, Leiden University, Kamerlingh Onnes Building, Steenschuur 25, 2311 ES, Leiden, the Netherlands.

E-mail addresses: e.fosch.villaronga@law.leidenuniv.nl (E. Fosch-Villaronga), c.j.calleja.ahmad@law.leidenuniv.nl (C.J. Calleja), h.g.drukarch@law.leidenuniv.nl (H. Drukarch), diego.torricelli@csic.es (D. Torricelli).

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literature about ISO 13482:2014 [7,8], a comprehensive overview of how such a standard addresses social and ethical issues for physical assistant robots is missing. Previous research has identified ethical and social issues raised by socially assistive robots [14,18,19] and physical assistant robots [2,5]. However, an effort to juxtapose these ethical and social concerns with the current norms and standards governing these robots is still lacking.

We bridge this gap in this article by carrying out a systematic literature examination of the issues that lower-limb exoskeletons pose ISO 13482:2014 on personal care robots addresses them. Though other standards are relevant to the design, construction and use of lower-limb exoskeletons, ISO 13482:2014 stands out as the most comprehensive safety standard tailored explicitly to robots that function in close proximity to human users, encompassing lower- and upper-limb exoskeletons. Notably, ISO 13482:2014 is a European harmonized standard, meaning that compliance is considered presumptive compliance with regulations and directives applicable within the European Union. Discussing ISO 13482:2014 is particularly timely as the new ISO/CD 13482 standard, set to replace it, is currently in the preparatory stage. This new standard may play a pivotal role in facilitating the introduction of robots in healthcare [19].

For these reasons, we intentionally delve into the specific shortcomings of ISO 13482:2014 with regard to exoskeletons to deeply explore the intricacies of this standard and its implications for ensuring safety within the scope of our study. This work focuses on lower-limb exoskeletons, underscoring the distinctive challenges that emerge from a kind of robot intricately intertwined with the user's body. Future work will cover socially assistive robots or, in the words of ISO, *mobile servant robots*.

We conclude that, even though ISO 13482:2014 has proved to be a significant step towards regulating wearable robots, it fails to reflect the ethical and social issues that robots present sufficiently. In this respect, developers often find themselves with unclear regulatory guidance that, most of the time, makes them fall short of integrating policy goals entirely. To solve this gap, we compile our findings in an accessible manner and provide concrete recommendations to help decision-makers overcome the drawbacks.

To an extent, our findings reflect the work conducted to translate environmental, social and governance concerns associated with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into specific parameters for the design and use of robots (cf [20]). In this sense, we emphasize the need for including provisions tailored to specific categories of people (4.1.5), expanding ISO 13482:2014's focus beyond physical safety to encompass aspects like privacy (4.1.6). The need for comprehensive requirements covering the entire lifecycle of robots, including recycling and proper disposal of components, which reflects environmental concerns, is discussed in section 4.4.5.

The paper sets the stage with a presentation of ISO 13482:2014's history, structure, and normative status within the European Union in section 2. A description of the methods for the systematic review follows in section 3. Section 4 presents regulatory gaps and inconsistencies in ISO 13482:2014, specifically in relation to lower-limb exoskeletons. It offers an insight into relevant areas for improvement and proposes specific action points to help decision-makers overcome the standard's drawbacks and revise the standard accordingly. Lastly, section 5 wraps up the piece by summarizing our results and presenting a set of extended conclusions to guide policymakers as they determine the path forward for improving ISO 13482:2014.

2. An overview of ISO 13482:2014

ISO 13482:2014 is a technical standard that sets forth provisions for adequately designing and manufacturing so-called 'personal care robots' (ISO 13482:2014 Section 1). The standard defines these as any 'service robots' whose function is to improve human users' 'quality of life' without being used for medical purposes like therapy or rehabilitation

(ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.13). This standard is the first to establish safety requirements for robots interacting closely with humans, used in serviceable contexts and daily living activities, excluding non-medical and non-industrial applications.

Three specific kinds of robots are the main focus of ISO 13482:2014. The first is the 'person carrier robot,' which enhances users' wellbeing by moving them from one specific point to another (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.16). The second category is the 'mobile servant robot.' Instead of transporting users, these robots carry or hold objects for them or merely engage in social exchanges with humans (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.14). Some of these robots have been used in different contexts, such as the hospitality industry or in industrial fairs [21].

ISO 13482:2014 calls the third category 'physical assistant robots.' What singles them out is that they offer physical assistance to users while performing certain activities (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.15). The kind of assistance that characterizes 'physical assistant robots' is specified in the standard as 'supplementation' and 'augmentation' (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.15). Whereas the former includes restoring capabilities to an average level, the latter instead focuses on enhancing human capabilities beyond the ordinary [7].

The ISO standard further classifies physical assistant robots into two categories: 'restraint-free' or 'restraint-type' robots (ISO 13482:2014 3.15.1 and 3.15.2). What distinguishes one class from the other is whether the device is attached to the human body while in use (ISO 13482:2014 3.15.1 and 3.15.2). In this sense, 'restraint-free' robots are not connected, whereas those classified as 'restraint-type' work insofar as they are attached to the user's body (ISO 13482:2014 3.15.1 and 3.15.2). Lower-limb exoskeletons fall within this latter category because the robot's joints are affixed to the user's lower limbs to provide support.

Although ISO 13482:2014 addresses hazards and safety measures for all the robotic devices specified above, the issues are often specific to each category specified above. The standard takes into account the complexity of installing the robot (including how it is installed, programmed, operated, and maintained) and the degree of interaction with humans. Not all hazards may apply to every personal care robot, and risks may be different from robot to robot, necessarily leaving room for variation in the safety requirements or protective measures to be implemented.

Recognizing that hazards associated with personal care robots might vary considerably, the standard includes provisions on risk assessment, safe design and safety measures, information for use, and validation and verification standards (ISO 13482:2014 Section 1). Concerning the risk assessment prescribed within ISO 13482:2014, the standard contains a non-exhaustive list of typical hazards (ISO 13482:2014 Annex A.1) (see Table 1).

Although this list seems comprehensive, the literature continues to highlight that ISO 13482:2014 fails to cover all the hazards associated with robots [7,8,22]. That argument also applies to lower-limb exoskeletons. For instance, while balance loss is the second cause of falls among older adults, travel instability measures do not apply to lower-limb exoskeletons (ISO 13482:2014 Annex A.1 Hazard item 59). Another example is that instability in a collision does not apply to

Table 1
Hazards identified under ISO 13482:2014.

Hazards identified under ISO 13482:2014 (Section 5)	
Charging batteries	Robot movement
Storage and supply of energy	Durability of the robot throughout its lifecycle
Actions after starting up	Erroneous autonomous decisions
Electrostatic potential	Exposure to moving parts like actuated joints
Shape and contact with external parts	Function that does not make humans aware of the robot
Emissions like noise and fluids	Conditions of the environment during use
Electromagnetic disruptions	Errors of navigation and localization
Mental stress and discomfort	

lower-limb exoskeletons, even though crashing against certain obstacles while having a robot affixed to their bodies could harm users (ISO 13482:2014, Annex A.1 Hazard item 62–63) [7].

The relevance of this issue cannot be overstated. Undoubtedly, ISO 13482:2014 is not the sole technical standard that pertains to the design and utilization of lower-limb exoskeletons for everyday activities. For instance, the IEC 62443 series, titled ‘Industrial communication networks - Network and system security,’ provides cybersecurity guidelines that are pertinent when exoskeletons incorporate information technology components. ISO 13482:2014 itself integrates a number of so-called ‘normative references’, meaning other standards that are necessary for its understanding and application. Among them are, ISO 14118 ‘Safety of machinery — Prevention of unexpected start-up’ and the ISO series 15534, ‘Ergonomic design for the safety of machinery’. In addition to safety concerns, certain standards have broadened the scope of considerations for the design and use of robots. The BS 8611 series of standards, for instance, covers a wider range of ethical issues, such as privacy and non-discrimination, which are relevant to exoskeletons as well.¹ In the same sense, the Japanese Standards Association (JSA)-Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS) B 8456–1 on Personal Care Robots specifies performance requirements, safety requirements and indication requirements of wearable robots for lumbar support on the basis of consensus reached between manufacturers, consumers and other neutral bodies [23].

Furthermore, since 2017, ASTM International’s Technical Committee on Exoskeletons and Exosuits (ASTM F48) [24–26] has been actively developing a series of standards addressing critical aspects of these technologies. These standards cover safety information (F3358-18 - ‘Standard Practice for Labeling and Information for Exoskeletons’), standard terminology for exoskeletons and exosuits (F3323-19 - ‘Standard Terminology for Exoskeletons and Exosuits’), and documenting environmental conditions for test methods used with exoskeletons (F3427 - ‘Standard Practice for Documenting Environmental Conditions for Utilization with Exoskeleton Test Methods’).

However, ISO 13482:2014 stands out as the sole standard specifically addressing lower-limb exoskeletons and acting as a European harmonized standard. European harmonized standards satisfy the fundamental safety conditions (ESRs) specified in both regulations and directives within the European Union. ISO 13482:2014 became a harmonized C-type standard under the Machinery Directive on 11 July 2014 (OJ C 220–11/07/2014) [27]. Once harmonized, the reference to the standard is disseminated within the European Union’s Official Journal, and those who can demonstrate that they have complied with it are presumed to meet the safety criteria included in the corresponding EU legislation. Hence, until the ISO/AWI 13482 standard replaces ISO 13482:2014, compliance with the conditions described creates a presumption of adherence with the requisites contained in the Machinery Directive (*Machinery*, Directive 2006/42/EC, Article 7(2)) (Calleja, [28]. Moreover, as a harmonized standard, it replaces any competing national standard. In this sense, harmonized standards, here ISO 13482:2014, ensure that different stakeholders can demonstrate compliance with the benchmarks applicable through the European Union.

Departing from the quasi-legal status assigned to ISO 13482:2014, if the industrial standard lacks adequate account for potential hazards and does not contain sufficient precautions to guarantee that humans are safe around robots, it could entail having robots in the market certified as safe that could nonetheless compromise the safety of users and third parties that interact with these novel technologies.

¹ As of the time of writing, the latest version is BS 8611:2023, published on 27 March 2023.

3. Methods

The findings described above indicate that ISO 13482:2014 falls short in providing a safeguard baseline for ensuring that human-robot interaction (HRI) is safe in personal care contexts. In order to understand this issue, we carried out a systematic literature review to identify the regulatory gaps and inconsistencies in ISO 13482:2014. To retrieve relevant literature systematically, we relied on a protocol based on the PRISMA template for systematic reviews (see Fig. 1) [29].

The literature review underpinning this report took place in two phases (cf [30]. (see Fig. 1). First, we performed a literature search for works in English included in six search engines and databases (i.e., Google Scholar, Scopus, SSRN, Web of Science, PubMed, [omitted for reviewing purposes], and IEEE Xplore). The review was conducted between October and November 2021 and covered journal publications, conference proceedings, preprints, reports, and book chapters written in English.

We reviewed the title, abstract, and keywords for the following terms: (“ISO 13482:2014”) AND (“personal care robots” OR “exoskeletons” OR “Physical Assistants”). The query logic was adapted to fit the syntax and operators used in each engine. A total of 76 works were retrieved from this search (see Table 2).

The second phase of the literature review covered the filtering of the retrieved results, which followed the following procedure:

1. We manually removed duplicates after checking the title and author. We identified six duplicates and removed them.
2. We assessed in terms of eligibility the remaining 70 works. We removed those works not meeting the criteria 1. and 2. specified above. Seven pieces were rejected at this stage.
3. We then searched for manual records. We reviewed the references of all the remaining 63 pieces. Eight works were pinpointed at this stage.
4. We reviewed the remaining 71 works and performed an additional eligibility assessment to include those papers about restraint-type physical assistant robots or whose assessment might apply to such devices.

The review excluded those papers that only apply to exoskeletons used for medical purposes like rehabilitation. The second selection criteria determined whether the identified work highlighted gaps and inconsistencies in ISO 13482:2014. Reference to the term ‘gaps and inconsistencies’ is made when one or more of the following conditions are identified:

1. Failure to include a risk scenario as a safety hazard;
2. Insufficient safety requirements;
3. Scarce methods to verify and validate performance and safety;
4. Lack of standards for information for use;
5. Failure to include a relevant standard as a normative reference, and
6. Language choices that make the application of the standard more difficult.

At the last stage, 55 works were excluded. The remaining 16 sources’ content was classified according to the main issue identified in the assessment. In this regard, we consequently identified categories of gaps and inconsistencies concerning ISO 13482:2014’s scope and definitions, hazards identification, standards for safe design and safeguards, information requisites, and validation and verification procedures.

4. Results and discussion

ISO 13482:2014 brought forward safety standards applicable to emerging lower-limb exoskeletons and, as such, is a noteworthy step in the development of these technologies. However, the framework has several limitations. As Brian Scassellati expressed in an interview back in

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the systematic review.

Table 2
Overview of the query logic and of the returned results.

Databases	Terms	Results
Scopus	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	3
SSRN	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	0
Google Scholar	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	≥50 ^a
[Omitted for reviewing purposes] Search Assistant ^b	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	23
Pubmed	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	0
IEEE Xplore	("ISO 13482:2014") AND ("personal care robot" OR "exoskeleton" OR "Physical Assistant")	0

^a Only the first 50 results were selected.

^b Omitted for reviewing purposes.

2014, ISO 13482:2014 is a ‘great start,’ but it might have given rise to the misconception that robots were a well-known tool and not an emerging technology whose risks remain unclear [31]. Scassellati further warned that there is little understanding about the functions of care robots, how they should improve users’ well-being, or the implications of their use for their safety [31]. Although it was revised in 2019 and remained unchanged, the standard fails to address significant issues and lacks the necessary guidelines to help developers tackle them from the design phase.

The following subsections compile the results from the systematic literature review. We identified several regulatory gaps in ISO 13482:2014 and provided for each issue some policy recommendations that, in section 4.7, are summarized in a table.

4.1. ISO 13482:2014 scope and definitions

4.1.1. Personal care is not defined, and thus the standard’s scope is unclear

Even though it defines the notion of ‘personal care robot’ and provides examples of devices, the idea of ‘personal care’ remains undefined in ISO 13482:2014 [32]. The use of the notion in everyday parlance is not of help either. *Personal care* commonly links to activities like walking, showering, or attiring [33][34]. However, that notion is not of help for robots regulated within ISO 13482:2014 because none of these devices, particularly lower-limb exoskeletons, can perform any of these functions [32].

Lacking a specific characterization of the concept of personal care and how it applies to robotic systems makes it difficult to know what kind of technologies, especially where they have different applications, fall within ISO 13482:2014’s scope. It may be clear that exoskeleton devices used to assist people who have lost motoric functioning or who suffer from spinal cord injuries to perform daily tasks more

independently than they could otherwise manage qualify as personal care robots under the ISO 13482:2014 standard. For other applications of these robotic devices, however, the standard's scope of application may not be as apparent. For instance, one might raise questions about the classification of exoskeletons used to carry heavyweights, such as those employed in industrial settings to alleviate physical strain or by first responders to enhance their capability to carry heavy equipment. These exoskeletons primarily aim to boost workplace efficiency and reduce physical burden rather than providing personal care, as understood in the traditional sense of the phrase. Consequently, their classification as personal care robots becomes uncertain. Likewise, there is room for debate regarding exoskeletons utilized in the realm of sports training to enhance athletes' performance, as their primary objective is to improve athletic abilities rather than addressing personal care needs.²

As a result of incorrect categorization, roboticists might put in place unsuitable safeguards [35]. Particularly, manufacturers and suppliers might comply with the incorrect standard if they do not know whether or not a specific exoskeleton qualifies as a device used for personal care. In particular, it might remain unclear whether bordering standards apply. For instance, ISO 13482:2014 expressly excludes industrial applications, which are regulated under ISO 10218-1:2011 Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for industrial robots — Part 1: Robots (See Section 1 Scope; See also ISO 10218-1:201 — Part 1: Robots, Section 1, Note 1) [36,37]. However, the distinction between industrial and non-industrial lower-limb exoskeletons remains unclear insofar as the meaning of 'personal care robot' is not expressly stated.

The consequence of that mischaracterization is that users might end up being exposed to risks that developers would have handled by employing the right instrument. In addition, manufacturers and other stakeholders in the supply chain might be exposed to sanctions and further responsibilities despite their intention to develop safe technologies [7,38].

In order to tackle this lack of preciseness, it is essential to define what *personal care* means for ISO 13482:2014. Section 3 of this standard includes a list of terms and definitions, which could be updated to explain personal care. Doing so will help manufacturers and suppliers understand whether they should develop the specific prototype following ISO 13482:2014 or apply a different standard. Alternatively, the notion of *personal care* could be replaced with another term that has more resonance within the community of roboticists. That seems to be the option that ISO/TC 299 has chosen in developing ISO/AWI 13482, a standard that will replace ISO 13482:2014. Indeed, the instrument's name does not include the term personal care. The Committee replaced it with 'service robots,' a more common notion within the community parlance. Indeed, ISO 8373:2012 ('Vocabulary') (2012) already defines that term [39]. Additionally, both the International Service Robot Association (ISRA) (Pransky, 1996) and the International Federation of Robotics (IFR) have had working definitions of service robots for many years [40]. Hence, it seems a more straightforward notion for roboticists than *personal care* and brings clarity to the scope of the technical standard.

4.1.2. The notion of 'personal care robot' is vaguely defined

As mentioned earlier, the term 'personal care' remains undefined. In addition, the existing literature highlights issues with respect to its application to robots. It is argued that the definition of *personal care robot* as covered in ISO 13482:2014 is inaccurate from a legal perspective. The standard defines it as those technologies whose purpose is to directly advance humans' life quality (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.13). However,

² In 2017, Eduard Fosch-Villaronga introduced the concept of a "RoboGym" where exoskeletons could be utilized to enhance muscle activity through exercise. Recently, in 2021, Enhanced Robotics, a company based in Hong Kong, released SPORTSMATE 5, a lower-limb exoskeleton specifically designed to improve athletes' physical performance and assist with workouts. See MyFitExo. (n.d.).

that idea is vague and therefore requires further specification and clarification. On the one hand, Fosch-Villaronga has argued that it is difficult to understand what the notion of 'improvement' conveys or whether it applies to every human interacting with the robot or to only a selected category of people (2019). On the other hand, the same scholar maintains that what 'quality of life' means relies on each subject's experiences and backgrounds, and thus it is hard to pinpoint [7].

It remains uncertain, for instance, whether lower-limb exoskeletons designed to augment human capabilities can be considered as 'improving life quality'. This includes exoskeletons used for tasks like carrying heavyweights outside industrial contexts, such as those employed by first responders to enhance their capacity for heavy equipment handling or those utilized in training and sports settings to boost users' endurance and physical abilities.

Vague definitions, particularly in a technical standard like ISO 13482:2014, are problematic because they lead to misconstruing the technologies falling within the scope of its provisions [35]. Though standardization has been conducted to define notions such as robot and robotics (see ISO 8373:2021 Robotics — Vocabulary; IEEE 1872-2015 - IEEE Standard Ontologies for Robotics and Automation [39,41]) ISO 13482:2014 stands apart as the sole standard utilizing the concept of 'personal care' to delineate its scope. Our literature review indicates that this notion introduces an element of ambiguity into the standard's scope which warrants attention.

In turn, an unclear scope implies that manufacturers and suppliers might ignore the benchmarks outlined in the standard if they consider that it does not apply to their developments. They might thus comply either with the wrong provisions or fail to integrate any safety standard at all. That ignorance might lead to sanctions because of inadequate adherence to the law. In addition, such a lack of clarity compromises the safety of users, who might end up exposed to risks that would have been foreseen by applying the right instrument [32]. Addressing this issue demands refining the definition of *personal care robot*. It is crucial to replace vague terms like improving quality of life with more precise notions. One option could be listing the applications falling within the standard or defining the services (e.g., transport, locomotion) that would put a robot under the standard's scope. Similarly to the previous issue, it is also possible to replace the notion of personal care robot with terms that have more resonance within the community. ISO/TC 299 seems to be following that path when it substituted 'personal care robot' for 'service robot' in ISO/AWI 13482. Likewise, in the more recent ISO 8373:2021 Robotics — Vocabulary, it appears that the term "personal care robot" has been replaced with "service robot." The latter is defined as a "robot in personal or professional use that performs beneficial tasks for humans or equipment" (3.7). Additionally, the entry includes explanatory notes providing various examples of both personal and professional applications. The former encompasses functions such as "physical support", which point to lower-limb exoskeletons.

4.1.3. The categorization of robots by function is confusing and might lead to excluding robots with the same capabilities

Classifying robots because of their intended function has also been criticized. Robots typically have different components and include software applications. Some authors have argued that, by focusing on the intended purpose, ISO 13482:2014 overlooks that aspect and leads to a scenario where manufacturers or suppliers choose the standards that their robots will follow [32]; cf [42].

The exclusion of exoskeletons used for military purposes is an example that can be brought forward to support this point. Those devices fall outside the scope of ISO 13482:2014, even if they have the same features as exoskeletons used in everyday activities. The consequence is that manufacturers or suppliers could, in theory, avoid the application of ISO 13482:2014 by claiming, even if identical, the robot at stake will be used in a warfare context [32]. The same happens with those robots that are intended for medical purposes. While the standard states that it does not apply to medical applications, it is also true that

these devices pose very similar risks to humans wearing the exoskeletons for rehabilitation purposes (ibid; [43]).

To improve ISO 13482:2014, ISO/TC 299 should consider replacing the categorization of robots by function or adding additional criteria. Roboticians need something more than the mere intended purpose to decide whether ISO 13482:2014 applies to a specific robot. Instead of the intended function, or in addition to it, the standard should list other factors. For instance, it could be required that robots, with and without a personal care purpose, shall fulfill the requirements of ISO 13482:2014 if their capabilities, or intended users, are similar to other devices regulated within the standard.

4.1.4. *The focus on personal care robots creates a category that is confusing*

ISO 13482:2014 includes many confusing categories that blur its scope. One of the most notorious confusions in healthcare is whether a device falls within the corresponding regulation, and thus is a medical device, or whether it does not. While ISO 13482:2014 aimed to clarify the field, it created many new confusing categories. The focus on personal care robots created an in-between category between service robots and medical devices: those for medical use and well-being. However, according to Regulation 2017/745 (Medical Devices), technologies with both medical and non-medical purposes fall within its scope. (*Medical devices*, Regulation 2017/745). This distinction is geared towards avoiding treating devices that present a similar risk to the user differently [8,35,44]. In this regard, the critical question is to what extent does ISO 13482:2014 provide any room for lower-limb exoskeletons at the crossroads between medical and non-medical technologies [43].

The problem with confusing categories is that manufacturers and suppliers might fail to comply with the proper regulation. In turn, that might expose them to sanctions and further responsibilities. In this sense, the surveys conducted within LIAISON, an H2020 COVR sub-project, revealed that robot developers with experience with ISO 13482:2014 run multiple standards for their devices [43]. They also believe that their robot does not fit into the standard category, do not know if it is a medical device, and have been confronted with different classifications from public and private policy documents. As a result of incorrect categorization and unclear classification, roboticians might put in place inadequate safeguards, and users might find themselves in risky or harmful situations (see also [7]).

In order to deal with the problem of confusing categories, ISO/TC 299 should update ISO 13482:2014 with guidelines to determine the differences, in terms of capabilities, function, and intended users, between those robots falling within the standard and those that fall outside its scope. That measure should provide the standard with a more precise scope to help manufacturers and suppliers determine whether ISO 13482:2014 is relevant for a specific device.

4.1.5. *The standard lacks specific requirements for different categories of people*

The users of exoskeletons have different shapes and sizes (Søraa & Fosch-Villaronga, 2020). Indeed, there are various criteria to determine for whom an exoskeleton is designed, like height, weight, and health condition. Despite the multiplicity of features and criteria, some authors have gathered evidence that these technologies are not developed with differences between users in mind [12,45]. On the contrary, the idea is to build devices that can fit as many people as possible, which often leads to considering typical attributes while disregarding those that are not common [13]. This approach appears to be followed by industrial standards, which often do not pay attention to users' unique characteristics (ISO 13482:2014 Introduction).

That approach appears to be followed by industrial standards, which fail to acknowledge users' unique characteristics. ISO 13482:2014 states that future editions will include more complete data on different categories of people (ISO 13482:2014 Introduction) like children or older adults. Some authors argue, however, that such a statement gives the impression that ISO 13482:2014 is nothing more than a provisional

standard and that vulnerable populations can wait for having standards incorporating safeguards for them [7,12]. In addition to those considerations, it is noticeable that the standard only recommends considering typical body sizes of the intended user population to avoid demanding postures or ensure easy operation (ISO 13482:2013 Section 5.9.2.1). However, it does not oblige manufacturers and suppliers to consider body shapes that are not typical and there is no requirement to inform users of the targeted population and whether the robot fits different categories of people (cf. ISO 13482:2013 Section 5.9.2.5).

While ISO 13482:2014 obliges manufacturers and suppliers to consider the 'conformity to the human anatomy and its variability' when identifying hazards (ISO 13482:2014 Section 4.2), the standard nonetheless lacks specific requirements to tackle those issues and is not specific on how the enshrined provisions safeguard different bodies, genders, and sexes [46]. Moreover, those considerations are restricted to anatomy, ignoring other aspects such as age, race, health condition, or even gender which is not the same as biological sex. In the end, because the standard provides no further guidance, it remains up to manufacturers to decide whether and how they should tackle the differences among end-users.

That problem brings about uncertainties regarding the protected scope of the framework for different types of users and questions around how diversity and inclusion as concepts are considered [13,15]. This complex issue is particularly significant for lower-limb exoskeletons and other wearable robots, which change how users experience themselves and their bodies [47–49]. Notwithstanding their advantages, these systems' embodiment and configurations directly impact the body to which they are attached and other individuals that interact with them. Thus, they can cause unanticipated or uncontrolled harm, particularly damage that cannot be easily rectified [50]. That raises important questions for the safety of specific users whom ISO 13482:2014 does not address. For instance, under which conditions can a pregnant woman safely wear a lower-limb exoskeleton? Were the differences in the pelvis of women and men considered when designing the exoskeleton? To what extent do those differences compromise the safety of a user? These are particularly relevant questions to raise, yet they remain unaddressed within ISO 13482:2014 [51].

Although the scientific community broadly supports the narrative that integrating gender and sex considerations in research makes a significant difference and contributes to better science [52–54], many disciplines nevertheless struggle to reflect those considerations in practice. Missing them in robotics development can lead to adverse consequences for society, from exacerbating existing biases and stereotypes to safety concerns in health-related applications [55,56]. With an eye on ISO 13482:2014, it is thus essential to stress the need to re-shape the standard in light of the different features of potential users and how those differences determine their interaction with an exoskeleton attached to their bodies.

To highlight the importance of considering the elderly, children, and pregnant women under ISO 13482:2014, several workshops were organized by the LIAISON Project.³ During these workshops, participants generally reported that they deemed such considerations fundamental. More specifically, participants presented concrete aspects that should be considered in relation to these different users, including cognitive capabilities, different learning ways, safety, different limit values, mental and physical vulnerabilities, different body dimensions, interaction requirements, mental culture, physical disabilities, interaction with the robot, situation comprehension, body-reaction time, and size physiology. In addition, participants indicated that there should not be a simplification of specific user groups and standard revision within this context [43,57,58].

³ See <https://www.laiden.org/projects/liaison-h2020-covr-project>.

4.1.6. ISO 13482:14 has a narrow focus on physical safety

ISO 13482:2014 focuses on avoiding injuries due using a robot. Even though these technologies include a software layer, and some of them might even use cloud services, the possibility of injuring humans has received the spotlight (Tucker et al., 2015).

Robots growingly interact directly with humans in the most diverse environments. Wearable robots, particularly lower-limb exoskeletons, have an even more intimate relationship as they assemble the human body. In some cases, that includes impaired individuals who would not walk or stand without connecting their bodies to the robot. For that reason, these technologies challenge how users perceive themselves and how others perceive them [5]. In such a scenario, safety cannot be ensured by merely fencing the robot. Moreover, it remains unclear how to conceptualize safety and the aspects it covers [16].

Safety is commonly understood as the state of being *safe*, i.e., freedom from the occurrence or risk of injury, danger, or loss.⁴ Although this shared concept, laws, regulations, and standards have adopted various definitions for different sectors, involving confusion, lack of clarity, and a lack of homogeneity in understanding what safety means [16]. For instance, the current Directive 2001/95/EC on General Product Safety defines safety in its Art. 2. b): “safe product shall mean any product which, under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use including duration and, where applicable, putting into service, installation and maintenance requirements, does not present any risk or only the minimum risks compatible with the product’s use, considered to be acceptable and consistent with a high level of protection for the safety and health of persons.” This legal definition of safe products is quite broad, and it can be understood as covering all kinds of risks that can, directly or indirectly, cause harm to consumers [16]. Although ISO 13482:2014 covers safety requirements for personal care robots, the standard does not define safety.

Some authors have pointed out that safety has been narrowly construed as applying to those hazards that may physically affect users [16]. That is the case of ISO 13482:2014, which seems to disregard other factors like privacy, security, or potential users’ psychological well-being - only mentions the stress factor [15]. However, those issues are critical in the case of technologies like lower-limb exoskeletons, which challenge a narrow understanding of safety [22]. Indeed, these devices might, for instance, modify the sense of autonomy and control over one’s body, or their interconnectivity might upset those who interact with a user wearing a robot [2]. Those issues nonetheless go far beyond an understanding of safety that is restricted to avoiding injuries [16].

Emerging lower-limb exoskeletons thus call for a more comprehensive notion of safety, as Martinetti et al. already made clear in (2021). These not only demand addressing issues of cybersecurity or cognitive hazards. It also calls for considering the implications of devices that might evolve due to the embedment of machine learning techniques [2, 7,38]. However, addressing those issues demands going beyond injuries to factor in the broader array of implications that exoskeletons have for human dignity [44].

4.2. Identification of hazards in ISO 13482:2014

4.2.1. ISO 13482:2014 does not fully cover close physical HRI

ISO 13482:2014 provides partial coverage of close physical HRI tasks, particularly sit-to-stand support [58]. According to ISO 13482:2014, developers should consider hazards due to ‘physical stress and posture’ (Section 5.9.2.1. General), and references are made to ISO 14738 regarding ergonomics. It also mentions that robots should be designed to have sufficient stability so that users do not need to undertake extraordinary measures to keep the device stable (Section

⁴ See <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/safety> & <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/safe>.

5.2.10.1 General). However, it does not provide adequate guidelines on the level of support a user needs to move from sit-to-stand and vice versa [58]. In addition, it remains undetermined how much force exoskeletons shall employ to make the movement safe.

The paramount variable in this discourse is the interaction pressure, which emerges as an instrumental factor tied to potential medical implications, including the ominous specter of blood vessel occlusion. The same amount of force exerted by exoskeleton motors can generate disparate interaction pressure levels in magnitude and distribution, leading to a wide range of hazardous events, such as bruising, skin abrasion, pressure sores, or soft tissue injuries. In this respect, different authors have explored the nexus between the magnitude of strapping pressure and the thresholds for human pain and discomfort [59,60]. This depended on several factors, such as the contact surface area, the shape and material of the cuff, and the body location where the cuff is exerting pressure. It is also relevant to consider that applying the same pressure statically or dynamically, i.e., when the exoskeleton is moving, can generate different physiological responses. For these reasons, this particular avenue of research underscores the empirical link between pressure and its physiological impact, amplifying its significance as a quantifiable metric in assessing the safety parameters of human-robot interaction. Importantly, pressure transcends the confinement of context, allowing for meaningful comparison across distinct scenarios—an attribute that holds compelling value in the quest for standardized evaluation. The pitfalls of sole reliance on force metrics become evident, for they fall short of encapsulating the multifaceted dynamics of human physiology and the intricate interplay between a device’s exertion and the consequential pressure it imposes.

There is also insufficient guidance on how these robots should adapt to different movement patterns (e.g., those of patients with a particular impairment or women). That deficiency is severe given the close physical interaction by which the robotic exoskeletons become part of the user’s body and assist her in performing the desired task.

Addressing that deficiency requires updating the standard with hazards from close physical HRI. More specifically, the standard should include:

- Adequate guidelines on the level of support a user needs in transitions from sitting to standing and vice versa;
- Further clarification on the level of force that restraint-type physical assistant robots shall exert to ensure the safety of movement, and
- More guidance on how these devices should adapt to different movement patterns.

4.2.2. ISO 13482:2014 lacks guidelines to secure safe interactions within public spaces

Exoskeletons modify users’ bodies and, thus, change how they perceive themselves and how others perceive them [5]. That modification is particularly relevant in public spaces, where individuals assembled with exoskeletons will enter into contact with other subjects. Individuals who once were impaired might walk again. Some others will enhance their abilities to, for instance, become more powerful. Addressing these questions from the early phases of development is critical to ensure that the risks that novel social interactions introduce are acknowledged and mitigated with design measures [2].

In the realm of service robots deployed in public spaces to transport objects or people or assist pedestrians [8], has pointed out the shortcomings of ISO 13482:2014. Given that users might wear them in everyday activities, including walking in public spaces and interacting with pedestrians, some of these considerations also apply to lower-limb exoskeletons.

The main problem with ISO 13482:2014 is that it overlooks the hazards of populated public spaces by only considering pedestrians as ‘safety-related objects’ to be protected from harm while disregarding specific requisites for robots interacting with users in shared areas (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.21.1) [8]. That insufficient characterization

ignores that, even if not causing harm, a user walking with a lower-limb exoskeleton might distress other pedestrians if the device is equipped with monitoring tools. Having an exoskeleton also might lead to particular interactions with other users or objects in a rush that the standard ignores. As [8] indicated, social norms and proxemics are also important. Exoskeletons modify users' bodies and sense of independence [2]. Thus, they change how users relate to others, and others relate to them. Again, the standard does not account for those particularities by characterizing pedestrians as mere safety-related objects (ISO 13482:2014 Section 3.21.1).

For lower-limb exoskeletons, it is noteworthy that ISO 13482:2014 does not consider vandalism a hazard nor includes guidelines on that matter. As [8] point out, even if ISO 13482:2014 mentions 'vandalism,' the definition seems to focus on protecting the robot from abusive behavior. It thus ignores that, for instance, a wheelchair user now wearing an exoskeleton might become more vulnerable if others can stop the device without her consent or manipulate the sensors to harm her. In general, not considering the implications of vandalism for robots used in everyday activities leads to designs that expose users who enter a public space while being assembled to a robot.

Apart from those issues, lower-limb exoskeletons might also impact how crowd flow is negotiated if the device is too bulky or does not correctly follow the user's gait pattern. Moreover, they might modify the nature of public spaces, as they will probably restrict access to these spaces if needed to avoid compromising the integrity of both robot and user. Some of these issues have already been acknowledged in the case of last-mile delivery robots and other devices operating in public spaces [8, 61,62]. However, the relevance of these problems for lower-limb exoskeletons, and other wearable robots, remains uncharted territory.

Acknowledging those issues, and requiring protective measures, is vital to ensure that wearable robots are suitable for activities of daily living. We recommend updating the standard with hazards arising from using physical-restraint robots in public spaces and considering the specific attributes of such areas. In particular, ISO 13482:2014 should pay attention to hazards concerning proxemics and social norms, crowd flow, and vandalism [8]. Should that influence, for instance, whether the robot should include a manual emergency stop? Shall the standard require a specific interface for users who wear an exoskeleton on a sidewalk? These are the conversations in which ISO/TC 299 should engage because they are currently unresolved.

4.2.3. Cognitive and psychological aspects arising from robot use currently lack

The interaction between humans and robots goes beyond the physical dimensions. In the case of some robots, like shopping assistants or tour guides, it seems clear that they engage in social relations with their users, thus challenging the narrow conception of safety as the mere avoidance of harm [7,16].

The same can be said of exoskeletons. Even if these technologies do not interact socially with persons, they might have significant implications for users' short- and long-term well-being [2,16]. Some authors have pointed out that robots might compromise people's psychological integrity (Lasota, Fong & Shah, 2017). Others have shown that some applications might challenge the ideas of acceptability or appropriateness in specific contexts [63]. Some researchers have found that working under poor psychosocial conditions may be correlated to worsening mental health and possibly unemployment (Stacey et al., 2017; [16]. Those findings point to the need to avoid prioritizing the industry's interests over workers' health, as outlined in the standard BS 8611:2016.

ISO 13482:2014 recognizes that both mental factors are as relevant as physical factors (ISO 13482:2014 Section 5.9.3.1). However, the standard limits its focus to stress and discomfort (ISO 13482:2014 Section 5.9.3) [8]. As Salvini et al. argue, those factors include stress deriving from continually using a robot or from the opaque design of the interface, as well as hazards because of uncomfortable positions, noise, or extreme temperatures (2021). This selection leaves aside critical

psychological hazards that can emerge when users interact with lower-limb exoskeletons. These robots might affect an individual's self-perception as they become part of the user's self [5,47–49,64]. That change might result in dependence on the technology [5,65,66] or challenge users' agency over their bodies [5]. Perceived or subjective safety is, that is, how harmful the user or others perceive the robot, and privacy can also result in psychological hazards (Lasota et al., 2017; Bartneck et al., 2009). Indeed, the user might feel anxious, surveilled, or even react with violence while using the device [7,67]; see also, concerning socially assistive robots, [14].

When it comes to lower-limb exoskeletons, it could also be the case that a user is afraid of standing in an upright position and walking normally after spending several years in a wheelchair. This feeling directly impacts how safe the person perceives the exoskeleton and how well they walk with it. The person's cognitive abilities could also prevent them from assessing how well they will perform with a robotic device that helps them walk again. However, despite the significant physical and psychological risks it might introduce, ISO 13482:2014 omits the fear of falling as a potential hazard [7]. Not considering such psychological factors disregards a vital element that shapes the subjects and makes it difficult for developers to know their nature, their consequences, and the required safety measures necessary to mitigate the risks they entail.

We thus suggest broadening the list of hazards associated with lower-limb exoskeletons. An excellent example of that alternative is BS 8611:2016, the standard of the British Standards Institutions tackling the ethical challenges posed by robots. Indeed, the limited list in ISO 13482:2014 is broadened in BS 8611:2016 by adding issues like humiliation, angst, addiction, or inattention [8,68]. The European Parliament further expanded the list in its report on Civil Law Rules on Robotics. It included sentimental connection as a hazard, notably concerning children, the elderly, and people with disabilities (European Parliament, 2017) (see also [8]. ISO/TC 299 should follow the same path and acknowledge the broader range of cognitive hazards introduced by robots interacting directly with users, particularly exoskeletons that work in symbiosis with the human body.

4.2.4. Overtrust as a source of hazards remains ignored

Trust requires considering whether others are worthy of our trust, typically in light of observed evidence [69]. Being trustworthy requires not only that the agent will not exploit the susceptibilities of the dependent party but that she will contribute to such a party's benefit [70]. Furthermore, it consists of the readiness to be held accountable [70].

However, trustworthiness is also context-dependent. It thus can mean many things depending on the specific context at stake. Indeed, trusting depends on the context and varies among cultures [69,71]. The following definitions encapsulate the typical definitions of trust as applicable to robots and, particularly, lower-limb exoskeletons:

- [72] define trust as a distinctive collective idea and association that can address susceptibility, uncertainty, risks, and anticipations (see Ref. [73].
- The definition that [74] use is slightly different. Instead of a collective idea, trust, in their opinion, is an attitude leading to perceiving an agent as favorable to the dependent party's objectives in a scenario of uncertainty and vulnerability (see also [69].
- In contrast [75], characterizes it as counting with the fact that others will not cause harm in a scenario of uncertainty. It thus involves at least two parties, the trustee, who is expected not to harm, and the trustor, who counts on the trustee (see also [76].
- [77] distinguish between trust based on an agent's benevolence and trust based on her integrity. The first notion focuses on the intentions, whereas the second notion highlights adherence to acceptable ethical principles.

The interaction with a robot could be frustrated if trust is not adequately addressed. Furthermore, both overtrusting and distrusting the robot might be a source of significant risks [69,75,78,79]. That issue is particularly prominent in lower-limb exoskeletons that work attached to the human body because they change how users perceive themselves and their vulnerabilities [2]. The levels of trust in one's abilities, or that of the robot, might increase the probability and impact of hazards. For instance, a user might overestimate the exoskeleton and disregard indications of malfunctioning, like a sensor failing. They might put her safety at risk with the additional risk of serious injuries [78]. Conversely, impaired users that walk again with an exoskeleton might underestimate their new capabilities, thus avoiding activities of their daily living. That activity avoidance brings additional hazards, and, in particular, it might increase the risk of falling in the future [80,81].

Despite its potential to compromise users' safety, ISO 13482:2014 does not consider that under- or overtrust, a psychological aspect, might result in physical hazards [82]. The standard focuses on *mental stress* but leaves open the problem of trust and how this trust impacts the robot's safety.

Given the intimate relationship between exoskeletons and users, ISO 13482:2014 should include under- and overtrust as safety hazards associated with restraint-type physical assistant robots. That might demand adding a new section with specific safety requirements and updating the list in Annex A.1. In that manner, it will be ensured that how the robot is trusted becomes part of manufacturers' and suppliers' risk appraisal.

4.2.5. ISO 13482:2014 does not consider hazards arising from contact with certain parts of the body

Since wearable robots, particularly exoskeletons, are cyber-physical systems, they might intentionally or unintentionally touch body parts. A lower-limb exoskeleton might put excessive pressure on a user's groin, causing pain. Because it is fastened to the human body, it might also touch certain body parts making users uncomfortable. These errors be a source not only of injuries or pain. They can also involve contact with intimate areas of the body, causing distress or humiliation [8,83–85].

Notwithstanding their potential impact, the hazard checklist from ISO 13482:2014 does not include possible hazards arising from contact with certain parts of the body [8]. That might lead to scenarios where wearing the robot is uncomfortable for users or, even if not, causes discomfort and embarrassment. Given the intertwinement between a user's body and the wearable robot, these technologies are not like any other technology. If unaddressed, a robot that touches the wrong parts might be a source of vulnerability for the user [5].

To tackle those vulnerabilities, ISO 13482:2014 shall include touching wrong body parts within the list of hazards. That would ensure that these issues are part of the manufacturer's and supplier's risk assessment. In this vein, they will reduce the risks to an acceptable level. Indeed, being conscious of reactions to touches from early phases could enable design choices that avoid hazardous contacts. Manufacturers and suppliers could tackle any residual risk by complying with requirements on information for use. Users will then understand, for instance, the kind of touches they will be exposed to if they assemble their bodies to a robot.

4.2.6. ISO 13482:2014 lacks guidelines on hazards deriving from vulnerabilities on the physical layer of robots

Robots can be considered cyber-physical systems. They combine hardware and software elements. Apart from specific communication processes and cloud services, they also include actuators and detectors [16,86]; see also [87]. Because of those features, a wearable robot can suffer from 'external vulnerabilities,' where malicious actors exploit the physical layer to compromise how the device handles data and functions [8].

In the context of lower-limb exoskeletons, this vulnerability can occur if malicious actors manipulate the triggers for protective or

emergency stops or if they tap on the sensors [7,88,89]. Under the Machinery Directive, the emergency stop button must be easily accessible (Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC, Annex 1 Section 1.2.4.3.). However, ISO 13482:2014 does not include the possibility that someone could tamper with such a button, compromising the safety of users. Yet, if the levels of security are communicated understandably, consumers tend to prioritize and even pay more for more secure interconnected systems (European Commission, 2020c; Johnson et al., 2020). Moreover, some robots might also be vulnerable to sticks, paints, or tapes obstructing their sensors [90]. Malicious actors might also hack external sensors to gain control of the robot [90]. They may do so, for instance, to make the user fall, those causing injuries. Despite the risks they introduce, ISO 13482:2014 does not consider any of these issues a safety hazard [8].

The first step to address those issues would be to update the standard with a list of potential safety hazards arising from external vulnerabilities. After updating the list, it is essential to define design measures, safeguards, and validation and verification methods geared explicitly toward tackling these vulnerabilities. Addressing them from the design phases while validating and verifying their performance will lead to more robust wearable robots.

4.2.7. ISO 13482:2014 lacks provisions on hazards deriving from vulnerabilities on the digital layer of robots

Malicious actors could also exploit the computational layer to take control of a robot without permission. They might also seek to delete or steal information or make it unavailable [5,15]. The exploitation of these 'internal vulnerabilities' might affect the robot's functionality and, in particular, compromise the safety of users. The situation is even more challenging in care settings, where robots interact closely with vulnerable users who might not be aware of the correct functioning of the robot [91].

For instance, a 'denial of service' might induce a lower-limb exoskeleton to stop providing walking support to a user who depends on it to move or keep balance (cf [90]). A malicious actor gaining control over a lower-limb exoskeleton could cause sudden movements, endangering users whose bodies are attached to the device. In general, an attack on a robot used for users' service, particularly when connected to their bodies as exoskeletons for the lower limbs are, might be a source of falls or unwanted yet dangerous movements.

The proliferation of operations across interconnected devices increases the opportunities for system failures and malicious attacks [16]; Michels & Walden, 2018). There is nonetheless scant knowledge on the ability of attackers to exploit the computational layer of robots not only in the industry [87] but also in social exchanges [92] and healthcare [93]. Moreover, it is unclear how exploiting those vulnerabilities compromises the safety of users that engage with the robot [16], especially when the robot is assembled with their bodies, and they depend on the device to walk or remain to stand.

Some authors have argued that, despite those risks, robots currently only have standard features suitable for many applications and, hence, overlook the specific vulnerabilities of these devices. Consequently, robots are susceptible to attacks trying to access and control their digital layer [8,90]. In addition, consumers and manufacturers prefer other factors, like development costs, marketing timing, prices, and usability, disregarding security concerns [94]. Yet, if the levels of security are communicated understandably, consumers tend to prioritize and even pay more for more secure interconnected systems (European Commission, 2020c; Johnson et al., 2020).

Unfortunately, ISO 13482:2014 lacks specific guidance on how to address those issues. The term 'hacking' was never mentioned in the standard [8]. ISO 13482:2014 illustrates the idea of *user interface* with examples of 'command devices' like systems for voice recognition or joysticks (ISO 13482:2014 Section 6.9.1; [8]). At the same time, it prohibits 'unauthorized use of controls or parameter changes,' including remotely accessing the robot, as a measure to tackle the risk of sudden

starting the robot or moving it against the will of users (ISO 13482:2014 Section 6.9.7; [8]). However, the main concern is not incursions exploiting the computational layer but that the user can press the incorrect switches and end up having access to the control device [8].

Additionally, ISO 13482:2014 does not include among the normative references any of the standards of the IEC 62443 series, which provides guidelines for cybersecurity in automation and control systems [8]. Given that including a standard as a normative reference makes it necessary for its application, adding the IEC 62443 series to ISO 13482:2014 would have made manufacturers and suppliers aware of the need to integrate cybersecurity solutions. In any event, current safety guidelines for personal care robots comparable to IEC 62443 are currently lacking [8].

In light of those vulnerabilities and the impact they might have, it is imperative to update ISO 13482:2014 with safety hazards arising from internal security vulnerabilities. The standard should include tools to help manufacturers and developers conduct a risk assessment to spot vulnerabilities exposing users to intrusions or malware. Defining safety measures right from the design stages is crucial. However, it is also important to define parameters for over-the-air updates and any other option to patch vulnerabilities spotted after commercializing a device. While requirements specific for the features of wearable robots are critical, a more attainable goal, at least in the short term, is to add standards from the IEC 62443 series to the normative references in ISO 13482:2014.

4.2.8. *Travel instability and instability in a collision is not recognized as a hazard associated with lower-limb exoskeletons*

Loss of balance is the second cause of falls among older adults [95], and, in general, obstacles can imperil normal gait (e.g., stairs, objects). Furthermore, using a robot in a public space presents the risk that pedestrians and bystanders might collide with the robot, pinch the user or strike her intentionally or unintentionally [8,96].

[8] have argued that the lack of guidance on those problems makes ISO 13482:2014 unfitting for safely interacting with robotic systems within public areas. The same can apply to exoskeletons, as the user walking with them can be considered an assemblage of a human and a robot [2]. On the one hand, travel instability measures do not apply to lower-limb exoskeletons and thus remain an unrecognized hazard within ISO 13482:2014 [7,15]. On the other hand, ISO 13482:2014 considers that lower-limb exoskeletons, and other robotic technologies that operate fastened to the user, present no risk of collision with people, animals, or other objects (ISO 13482:2014 Annex A.1 Hazard item 62–63). In concrete, it states that collisions with safety-related objects, other robots, “fragile” safety-related objects, walls, and permanent/unmovable barriers “are not applicable to restraint-type physical assistant robot.” This is a problem for lower-limb exoskeletons because, within the “hazards due to localization and navigation errors” section, the standard itself mentions “navigation errors preventing reaching of goal location or avoiding safety-related objects” [67]; p. 162–168). In using exoskeletons, these obstacles can impact balance, which can also be a safety hazard due to environmental conditions or unexpected terrain, but also for the transition switching, which can provoke a fatality for the user (Tucker et al., 2015).

Those limitations leave designers and users without guidance on calculating the risks of collision and consequent falls [7] when developing or using lower-limb exoskeletons [97]. For this reason, it is convenient to associate travel instability and collision with safety objects among the hazards that could arise from the use of restraint-type physical assistant robots. That would promote the development of design measures, safeguards, verification and validation methods, and parameters to inform users of the residual risks.

4.2.9. *ISO 13482:2014 does not address hazards coming from the estimation of movement*

ISO 13482:2014, while comprehensive in its scope, notably lacks

consideration for hazards stemming from movement estimation, overlooking potential risks that can arise from inaccurate estimations [8]; Calleja, Drukarch, & Fosch-Villaronga, 2022). A pivotal realization emerges—that movement estimation and execution introduce a level of risk for individuals but ISO does not address hazards arising from slow feedback and error connection. An example of novel risks is an imperfect synchronization or transmission mishap with a robot. Particularly for lower-limb exoskeletons, safety depends on the device’s motion. The implication is that estimating movement and its execution presents a risk for individuals. Hence, movement estimation should be accurate compared to the user’s own gait, even if internal and external factors, like a sneeze, may condition it [44]. The transition time between a user’s own intentional movement and the consequent reaction of the exoskeleton should be quick to impede the user from losing balance. Overall, making the robot responsive to the user movements remains an unresolved problem, especially for technologies expected to be used in unstructured environments, like houses or open spaces ([7,44,98]).

Given these critical observations, there lies a compelling case for updating ISO 13482:2014 with a comprehensive examination of the hazards that may stem from wrong movement estimation. Such an update should include a comprehensive elucidation of the design measures necessary to avert slow or imprecise responses to user intentions. Moreover, it should address the information users need about how their natural gait might evolve as they interface with robotic entities. In this context, the efficacy of testing as a reliable means of assessing the performance and safety of exoskeleton feedback systems deserves careful consideration [99]. Although ISO 13482:2014 was revised in 2020, there are still some questions unanswered: What design measures are necessary to avoid slow or inaccurate responses to the user’s intentions? What should users know about how their gait will change as they merge with a machine? Is testing a reliable method to assess the performance and safety of an exoskeleton’s feedback? Answering these questions is crucial to ensure a safe interaction between humans and robots assembled to their bodies.

4.3. *Identification of inherently safe design measures*

4.3.1. *ISO 13482:2014 lacks guidelines on time factors affecting robot use*

Some authors have argued that users need time and practice to adapt to having a robot [100], mainly when the device is supposed to act fastened to the body and provide support. Additional factors include how familiar the user is with robots, whether she has had previous experiences with these technologies, or how she perceives them. Those factors impact the interaction, particularly because familiarity impacts how the user attaches her body to robotic technology and engage in everyday activities that, in some cases, would have been beyond her abilities. Despite the prominence of those issues, ISO 13482:2014 does not include guidelines on the spiral of adaptation and how it affects users’ and other persons’ safety [7].

Generally speaking, the rate of technology innovation is not proportional to the robot operators’ skill development [56]. In other words, it remains unclear whether there needs to be specific training geared to caregivers and another one for users beforehand, during, and after. It is also unclear whether there should be some information and what kind of information should be provided to the users to enhance such a spiral of adaptation. While manufacturers are incorporating fault tolerance principles into the design of robots to mitigate risks [101,102], the erroneous employment of healthcare tools continues to be a substantial cause for medical mistakes [103–105]. For instance, in the context of Robot-Assisted Surgery, user errors generally occur where surgeons or a member of their team operate the surgical robot incorrectly, possibly due to lack of adequate training [56]. Also, in the context of healthcare service robots, several studies have already indicated a strong need for instructions to the staff, preparation, and engagement [106]. Such a demand also applies to collaborative robots and, in particular, lower-limb exoskeletons that work connected to the human body.

Perhaps one of the most formidable challenges of designing wearable devices is that the users' bodies change over time. For instance, children grow, and their bodies change over time. That factor impacts how a lower-limb exoskeleton can serve the needs of users [12]. Indeed, a robotic exoskeleton is likely to become unfitting for children considerably quickly [12]. In turn, the conditions of adults tend to deteriorate with age. One possible solution could be to have modules that can adapt as the user changes. However, that solution is difficult to implement in practice [12].

ISO 13482:2014 only mentions that information for use shall 'include the need for proper training to avoid operator travel time being longer than recommended' (ISO 13482:2014 Section 5.9.2.4). However, the standard does not clarify how long the adaptation period should be or how to assess users' changing abilities. The standard also has gaps concerning how hazards and safety requirements would change given the user's changing needs due to their progressive condition regarding either physical or cognitive abilities [58]. Moreover, if the user feels discomfort, she might adjust to the device. However, ISO 13482:2014 does not guide how much a robot could be adapted for safe use (cf [107]). These could significantly impact users' ability to use the system safely and compromise it if misused.

Given those gaps, we suggest that the standard requires taking into account changing abilities while designing wearable robots. The demand for proper training in requirements on information for use (ISO 13482:2014 Section 5.9.2.4) is crucial. However, it is also essential to design robots to account for the worsening or improvement of physical and mental abilities. Ensuring a safe spiral of adaptation is also crucial. Exoskeletons work to the extent that they are connected to the human body. Hence, an inadequate connection because, for instance, the user feels weird or embarrassed with the exoskeleton might compromise its safety. The standard should thus include design measures such that the robot performance follows the user's adaptation to it.

4.3.2. ISO 13482:2014 provides insufficient guidance on transparent HRI

The implications of transparency for robotics remain an uncharted territory, nonetheless significant steps, as IEEE-P700, a group devoted to systems transparency, shows [70]. The main focus of current research is the explainability of systems, be it from the robot's perspective or from that of the user. That has led some to highlight the disadvantages of transparency, like misconceptions and undesirable assumptions (Fischer, 2018). Overall, there are technical limitations (Koops & Leenes, 2014) to designing transparent devices, along with the risk of prioritizing seeing over actually comprehending (Ananny & Crawford, 2018).

The problem here is that ISO 13482:2014 lacks provisions for transparency in the interaction [8,108]. If transparency means making the device's intentions understandable, that is key for lower-limb exoskeletons. Users need to predict how the device will move to allow more appropriately or adapt their gait to the device. For instance, if an exoskeleton is about to move from stand to sit, the user should be able to know in advance that the robot will perform that movement. That would also provide enough time to spot wrong undesired decisions and stop them before they cause harm to the user.

ISO 13482:2014 nonetheless only requires that autonomous decisions are not harmful to users (ISO 5.12.1) [8]. It also instructs limiting the scenarios for operation or having robust sensors (ISO 13482:2014 Section 6.3). In contrast, manufacturers and suppliers are required to be mindful of the design of the interface (ISO 13482:2014 Section 6.9) [8]. In this sense, the exoskeleton should indicate whether it is on or off or incorporate specific warnings of its status (ISO 13482:2014 Section 6.9.2). However, none of these requisites answers the question of transparency for lower-limb exoskeletons, that is, whether the device's movements are understandable to the user who has her body fastened to a robot (see Ref. [8]). Given the intimate assemblage between robotic exoskeletons and their users' bodies [5], that kind of transparency would allow users to respond better in cases of erroneous movements or

other wrong decisions of the robot.

Some authors included in the review have also argued that the battery levels should be transparent to the user [7]. As powered devices, exoskeletons might end up without enough battery, on some occasions, only after some time. If the user does not know how much battery the exoskeleton has and, yet, depends on it to remain to stand, she might end up suffering harm [7]. For this reason, it is argued that the standard should require manufacturers and suppliers that robots indicate not only the level of battery but also the kind of movements that users can perform with the current status [7].

4.3.3. ISO 13482:2014 lacks safety requisite concerning third parties interacting with the robot

In contrast to animals described in detail, ISO 13482:2014 does not include detailed descriptions of how third parties might interact with the robot [8] and, especially, with a user assembled to a robot.

Indeed, the standard does not include much information on guaranteeing that trainers, pedestrians or bystanders are only affected to an acceptable level except for collisions (e.g., ISO 13482:2014 Section 5.14.1). The interaction modalities only cover the user and the robot [8]. That insufficiency fails to capture all the possible interactions between third parties and robots affixed to a user, like negotiations in traffic, proxemics, or distress due to sensors.

In particular, lower-limb exoskeletons in public spaces should distinguish between malicious contacts and those that are not, mainly if the user is to be secure while performing everyday activities [8]. One example relates to trainers and experts who would help users adapt to the exoskeleton. ISO 13482:2014 establishes that the information for use shall include 'the need for proper training' (Section 5.9.2.5). However, it says nothing about the design measures and safeguards developers should implement to protect those who prepare others to use the robot. Thus, a robot might be safe for the user but a source of hazards for trainers—and other third parties interacting with the exoskeleton for some reason.

4.4. Definition of safeguard measures

4.4.1. ISO 13482:2014 does not include sufficient instructions to deal with unavoidable or existing falls

Ideally, robots will be safe enough to render falls rare. Nonetheless, in the case of lower-limb exoskeletons, where the robot operates connected to the bodies of users, the possibility of falls cannot be excluded. Without standardized strategies to deal with them, users might suffer injuries. For instance, Van Herpen and colleagues (2019) report a case where a user's partner erroneously pushed a button, activating a graceful collapsing mechanism and causing an intra-articular fracture of the left tibial plateau to the exoskeleton user. However, the immediate cause of the fracture was that the user activated the exoskeleton right after it collapsed, but the device did not detect that her lower extremities were misaligned due to the previous collapsing. That case highlights that it is necessary to include guidelines on how to restart the device or recommend technical measures to impede a faulty restart to keep users safe.

ISO 13482:2014 nonetheless focuses on developing the robotic device to avoid falls. It lacks guidelines on responding once a fall has already occurred or is unavoidable [7]. The standard mentions that the device should have sufficient energy storage to allow recovery to a safe state following a power failure (Section 5.3.3.2) and refers to the requirements of ISO 14118 (Section 5.3.3.2) to avoid unexpected start-ups. However, it does not specify strategies for protecting users from injuries once falling becomes inevitable [7]. A technical solution could be ingrain an airbag that inflates once a potential fall is detected [7]. Relatedly, ISO 13482:2014 fails to specify in which circumstances are users allowed to restart the device manually or whether an automatic restart is a better alternative (see Section 6.2.2.3).

We suggest including safeguards to address the scenario where falls

have already occurred or are unavoidable. A robot that interacts intimately united to the human body in activities of daily living will likely end up involved in falls. These are not unavoidable. Manufacturers and suppliers thus need guidelines on the measures they should implement to deal with inevitable or materialized falls. In particular:

1. ISO 13482:2014 shall ensure that users of the standard develop exoskeletons that are restarted after a protective stop without rebooting or turning off and on software applications (ISO 13482:2014, Sections 6.2.2.2 and 6.2.2.3).
2. ISO 13482:2014, sections 6.2.2.2 and 6.2.2.3, shall include detailed requirements on the user's posture and steps to reactivate the device and make them dependent on a risk assessment.

4.4.2. ISO 13482:2014 lacks instructions about residual faults (bugs) in the software

Manufacturers and suppliers must address residual faults (bugs) in a lower-limb exoskeleton's software (Guiochet et al., 2021). For instance, a software bug in a lower-limb exoskeleton might lead it to move uncontrollably while the user is in certain positions, thus presenting the risk of injuries. That is particularly problematic with devices incorporating some form of autonomy, like an exoskeleton that follows a pre-determined gait pattern to support the user [109]. As they become more autonomous, the software becomes more complex, and, with it, new software bugs are introduced (Guiochet et al., 2021).

Despite these issues and the risks they pose, ISO lacks requirements for avoiding faults in the software layer (Guiochet et al., 2021). Unanswered questions are to what extent manufacturers and suppliers should implement over-the-air updates to correct defects on the software. There is also a lack of provisions on the impact of those bugs on users' physical safety. Is it an acceptable risk that an exoskeleton starts shaking while assembled to a user that needs its support? Is it an acceptable fault that the software controlling the robot needs to be restarted each time a protective stop is triggered? These are questions that ISO 13482:2014 has not answered yet. It is thus key that the ISO/TC 299 starts defining safeguard measures so that developers and suppliers can deal with them appropriately.

4.4.3. ISO 13482:2014 is unsuitable for regulating domain-safety functions

ISO 13482:2014 is designed to provide domain-specific functions with corresponding confidence levels. These are protective and emergency stops, as well as limits to the space where the robot can safely operate.

As Guiochet et al. (2021) argue, that approach is only suitable when we can separate the different functions from the central controller. However, to ensure that interaction, it is necessary to assign the central controller of the robot to a higher level of integrity in order to differentiate between needed movements and those that imply a collision (Guiochet et al., 2021). That is key to avoiding unintended movements when the robot is fastened to the human user. Indeed, a misperceived collision might lead the exoskeleton to move in a way that leads the user to lose balance.

4.4.4. ISO 13482:2014 lacks parameters for protective stops

The pragmatic approach for ensuring safety in commercialized robotic solutions is to power down and stop the robot if something goes wrong. However, this approach seems no longer viable regarding many emerging technologies. In many cases, removing the power from a robot supposed to support a user who depends on it may not be safe during a specific movement, e.g., climbing stairs (Guiochet et al., 2021). Particularly concerning lower-limb exoskeletons, that strategy might lead to the risk of triggering a protective stop in the circumstances where halting the device would increase the risk of injuring the user (e.g., when a user is about to sit down, and then the robot stops directly and leaves the person standing up).

Relatedly, there is no method to determine the space where a

protective stop can be activated, that is, the area(s) where the robot should or should not stop [88]. ISO 13482:2014 mentions that the robot should notify the user of its status if the battery falls below a certain threshold (5.3.3.3.). Those that can trap humans in isolated locations shall also include means of summoning assistance (5.3.3.3.). However, the standard does not mention whether there are specific spaces where the device shall not stop providing support, like crowded areas or while walking on stairs. Users might thus suffer additional injuries if the robot stops in a circumstance where support is essential for avoiding falls or preventing collisions.

Users' perception of control might also be impaired if they cannot stop the robot. Given that these devices cannot perceive how users feel, having a protective stop in a reachable place is critical to halt the robot when needed. Some of those features might help prevent malicious attacks where, for instance, someone triggers a button that is not reachable to the user. In contrast to ISO 13482:2014, the Directive 2006/42/EC determines that protective stops should be not only reachable but also visible (*Machinery*, Directive 2006/42/EC Annex I 1.2.4.3.) [7].

In light of the different issues arising from the lack of parameters for protective stops, we suggest:

1. Update ISO 13482:2014, Sections 6.2.2.2 and 6.2.2.3, to add that robot stopping functions, particularly emergency and protective stops, should be designed to activate them in case of an emergency easily or when safeguarding or risk reduction so demands.
2. ISO 13482:2014 should include the requirement to alert users of restraint-type physical assistant robots of the activation of an emergency stop (Sections 6.2.2.2 and 6.2.2.3). Consider leaving users sufficient time to invalidate the stop or move into a safe space.
3. Include a clause stating that manufacturers and suppliers should perform a risk assessment to determine the space where the removal of power is safe and would not cause additional hazards. In those circumstances, the robot might have a protective stop that does not result in power being removed but results in, for instance, monitoring the condition of the device, summoning assistance, or safely collapsing into a specific position.

4.4.5. ISO 13482:2014 lacks requirements for the robot's entire life cycle

ISO 13482:2014 states that it sets requirements covering the robot's complete life cycle (Introduction). However, that statement does not reflect the standard's content. Indeed, the entire life cycle is generally intended as encompassing either reassembling the robot or recycling or disposing of it, and ISO 13482:2014 does not include guidance on any of those processes [110]. An apparent reason is that life-cycle assessment procedures for robot technology do not exist yet, even if they have been explored in the literature in other fields (Giesen et al., 2020).

In light of that deficiency, ISO 13482:2014 should be updated with safeguard measures covering the robot's complete life cycle. Defining standards to remanufacture an exoskeleton, or recycle it, is critical to ensure that robots are safe not only while in use but also in further stages.

4.5. Information for use

4.5.1. Information for use in ISO 13482:2014 is incomplete and do not include third parties

'Information for use' (ISO 13482:2014 Section 8.1) is meant primarily for informing end-users about the use, potential uses, and risks of a particular device. Given the lack of information considering other safety dimensions [16]; how the action of the robot can be transparent to the user [70]; whether overtrust could lead to regrettable risks for the users [69]; or how time and changes could compromise user safety, we can conclude that the information for use in ISO 13482:2014 is not complete.

First, there is no requirement in ISO 13482:2014 to inform users of the targeted population on whether the robot fits different categories of

people, like women and the elderly (cf. ISO 13482:2013 Section 5.9.2.5). Second, ISO 13482:2014 mentions that information for use shall ‘include the need for proper training to avoid operator travel time being longer than recommended’ (Section 5.9.2.4). However, third parties have no information, such as the trainers, family members, or bystanders [67]. Third, even if ISO 13482:2014 is made to instruct manufacturers and suppliers to write down user information, the standard remains silent on how they should implement such a requirement [7].

The standard thus needs to be thoroughly revised to determine the kind of people that are likely to interact with lower-limb exoskeletons, what type of information is required to target them and how manufacturers and suppliers can comply with the standard. Different categories of users shall be taken into account, as well as third parties like trainers, family members, or bystanders.

4.6. Verification and validation methods

4.6.1. ISO 13482:2014 lacks safety test measures and measurement criteria

There is a lack of methods to assess whether robots perform as intended and whether they meet the requirements outlined in safety standards [107]. Additionally, there is a lack of physiological benchmarks to provide data about the effects of long-term use of exoskeletons [88,107,111,112]; Guiochet et al., 2021).

Similar gaps have been identified in the realm of rehabilitation robots, with some scholars proposing procedures to validate safety during design phases [113]. Concerns regarding validation and verification methods for robots used in everyday activities, as is the case with lower-limb exoskeletons, have also appeared in a recent technical report, which recognizes that most of the testing methods for these technologies have not been implemented or evaluated for accuracy and reproducibility (ISO/TR 23482-1:2020 Robotics — Application of ISO 13482 — Part 1: Safety-related test methods) [114]. However, ISO/TR 23482:2020 as a guide supporting ISO 13482:2014 for personal care robots, does not cover exoskeletons used as medical devices. For medical device regulation, ISO EN 14971:2019 is referenced, but the unique challenges posed by exoskeletons due to their autonomy and energy exchange with patients is not specified sufficiently in terms of risk assessment and reduction. ISO IEC 80601-2-78:2019 [115] is cited as a standard specifically addressing safety and performance requirements for medical robots, particularly in rehabilitation applications. However, this creates confusion on towards what are the safeguards needed to ensure safety in similar robot applications. To this end, as the medical device regulator extended the medical device protective scope to cosmetics because colored contact lenses presented the same risks to the human eye as the prescription ones; it becomes increasingly important if the regulator will do the same for exoskeleton technology which is increasingly used in multiple contexts such as personal care, rehabilitation, and the industry [44,112].

The need to formalize how information is collected and analyzed and which benchmarks are used is vital to ensure that developers assess performance and safety uniformly [107]. Otherwise, it will remain unclear whether safety standards are being met, and it will become challenging to apply ISO 13482:2014 in practice. Indeed, the lack of agreed procedures might impede the application of safety standards, as developers will not be able to determine that the design decisions they make fit the requirements contained in the standard.

4.6.2. ISO 13482:2014 does not have useable HRI models

The removal of fences leads to a direct interaction between humans and robots. With lower-limb exoskeletons, interaction is even more intimate, as the device operates connected to the limbs and in coordination with users’ movements [116]. In this scenario, several challenges appear when forecasting the consequences of faults:

1. It is difficult to determine causality because decisions are complex and, in some cases, do not follow determined patterns.
2. Hazards may only materialize in the long-term, mainly due to a series of choices and not to an isolated event of a combination of occurrences.
3. Uncertainties in how humans interact with robots and how they perceive them might lead to hazards that manufacturers and suppliers cannot forecast with the help of existing techniques and models to assess risks (Guiochet et al., 2021).

ISO 13482:2014 includes a review of task-based risk assessment as a way of verifying and validating the safe performance of personal care robots (Section 7 G). However, there is no functional modeling of the interaction between humans and robots (Guiochet et al., 2021). As a consequence, it is not possible to accurately forecast what kind of risks such interaction will introduce (Guiochet et al., 2021). Consequently, developers lack a systematic way of understanding how robots impact users and third parties and what kinds of hazards these devices introduce.

4.7. Overview of the ethical and social considerations of robotic exoskeletons to be accounted for in ISO 13482:2014

This following Fig. 2 summarizes the work conducted in this paper:

5. Conclusions

Following a systematic literature review, our findings support the conclusion that, even though ISO 13482:2014 has proved to be a significant step towards regulating wearable robots, it fails to address safety sufficiently and comprehensively. We have identified six different areas in ISO 13482:2014, which leave considerable room for improvement, and included policy recommendations for each of them (as summarized in Appendix A). While the standards landscape boasts diversity in consideration to be accounted for in relation to the design, construction and use of lower-limb exoskeletons, ISO 13482:2014 stands out as the sole European harmonized standard explicitly designed for lower-limb exoskeletons and other robots interacting with users in their daily lives. Shedding light on its shortcomings, particularly within the context of its ongoing review, has the potential to elevate the entire standardization framework and ensure a proper account for all relevant considerations.

The results suggest that ISO 13482:2014 requires improvements along different areas ranging from its scope to the definition of hazards to how gender and psychological considerations affect safety. In particular, the standard could be improved by having more specific definitions of the protected scope and the differences and intertwinements that these devices may have with other relevant pieces of legislation, mainly the Medical Devices Regulation. This line of thought shows several elements that, while they may not be traditionally considered part of the ‘physical safety,’ affect it considerably. If a patient has cognitive disabilities, it is likely that if these are not accommodated, the device may not be as safe as certified. Also, if gender and sex considerations are not considered (although they were acknowledged as necessary in the original standard), robot developers may ignore these aspects that may have ulterior adverse consequences for specific categories of users.

Overall, ISO 13482:2014 standard leaves some room for improvement before it provides enough guidance to developers to cover related safety-related issues for lower-limb exoskeletons. Our research, and that of others [7,8] gives indication that, while ISO 13482:2014 encompasses a diverse range of robots within its scope, this approach creates confusion about the adequate level of safeguards needed to ensure the safety of the robot’s operation [32]. As highlighted in the literature [2,7,14,35], robots largely differ in embodiment and context of use, so policy-makers have difficulty creating frameworks setting clear boundaries for

SCOPE & DEFINITIONS	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	Section 3 'Terms and definitions'	ISO 13482:2014 lacks a definition of personal care that is clear and consistent with the state of the art (4.1.1)	Define personal care or use a different concept (e.g., service robot) as a basis to define the standard's scope.
	Section 3 'Terms and definitions', 3.13	ISO 13482:2014 lacks a precise definition of personal care robot (4.1.2).	Define what should be understood under the phrase 'to improve the quality of life of humans' in order to further specify the meaning of the term personal care robot.
	Section 3 'Terms and definitions', 3.14-3.16	ISO 13482:2014 inadequately categorizes robots depending on their intended function (4.1.3)	Update the standard with a clause stating that robots with similar capabilities shall comply with the same requirements despite their intended function, thereby moving away from the focus on robot function towards robot capabilities.
	Section 1 'Scope'	ISO 13482:2014 has many confusing categories that blur its scope (4.1.4)	Update the standard with guidelines to determine the differences and clearly distinguish between personal care robots (falling within ISO 13482:2014's scope) and medical devices (falling outside ISO 13482:2014's scope).
	Introduction	ISO 13482:2014 fails to provide specific guidelines on different users groups (4.1.5)	Update the standard with more specific requirements for different categories of people (e.g., (pregnant) women, children and elderly people) and particular types of personal care robots, in addition to accounting for varying series of user criteria (e.g. height, weight, and health condition).
	Section 1 'Scope'	ISO 13482:2014 merely focuses on physical safety, ignoring other aspects like privacy, dignity, data protection, and personal autonomy (4.1.6)	Broaden the safety definition included in the standard so as to include other aspects beyond mere physical safety.

Figure 2. Overview of the ethical and social considerations of robotic exoskeletons to be accounted for in ISO 13482:2014

IDENTIFICATION OF HAZARDS	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	Section 5.10.9, Annex A.1, 74-76	ISO 13482:2014 fails to fully cover close physical HRI (4.2.1)	Update the standard with hazards arising from close physical HRI. More specifically, the standard should 1) provide adequate guidelines on the level of support a user needs in transitions from sitting to standing and vice versa; 2) provide further clarification on the level of force that a restraint-type physical assistant robots shall exert to ensure the safety of movement; and 3) provide more guidance on how these devices should adapt to different movement patterns.
	Section 5.15, 5.10.5, 5.10.8, 5.10.6, Annex A.1, 32-36, 62, 65-66, 69-73	ISO 13482:2014 does not cover hazards common in public spaces (4.2.2)	Update the standard with hazards arising from using physical-restraint robots in public spaces and consider the specific attributes of such spaces. In particular, attention should be paid to hazards concerning proxemics and social norms, crowd flow, and vandalism.
	Section 5.9, Annex A.1, 48-55	ISO 13482:2014 lacks details on cognitive and psychological hazards resulting from HRI (4.2.3)	Extend the standard's list of mental hazards that might emerge when users interact with lower-limb exoskeletons. Among others, include fear of falling, anxiety, deception and emotional attachment. The BS 8611:2016 and the European Parliament report on recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics can offer a fruitful basis for such expansion.
	Section 5.9, Annex A.1, 48-55	Overtrust as a source of hazards remains ignored in ISO 13482:2014 (4.2.4)	Update the standard with hazards arising from overtrusting the robot.

Figure 2. (continued).

	Annex A.1, 74-76	ISO 13482:2014 does not consider hazards due to a robot touching wrong body parts (4.2.5)	Update the standard with hazards arising from touching or exerting pressure on certain parts of the body.
	---	ISO 13482:2014 does not include hazards deriving from the exploitation of external vulnerabilities (4.2.6)	Update the standard with safety hazards arising from external security vulnerabilities (e.g., manipulation of emergency stops, or sensor obstruction).
	Section 6.9.7	ISO 13482:2014 does not include hazards deriving from the exploitation of internal vulnerabilities (4.2.7)	Update the standard with safety hazards arising from internal security vulnerabilities (e.g., intrusions, malware), and link to existing normative frameworks (e.g. IEC 62443).
	Section 5.10.3-5.10.5 Annex A.1, 59, 62-63	Travel instability and instability in a collision is not recognized as a hazard associated with lower-limb exoskeletons (4.2.8)	Link instability in a collision and travel instability to restraint type physical assistant robots, and provide for specific safety requirements in this regard.
	---	ISO 13482:2014 does not recognize hazards coming from estimation of movement (4.2.9)	Update the standard with hazards arising from slow or mistaken estimation of user movement.
INHERENTLY SAFE DESIGN MEASURES	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	---	ISO 13482:2014 lacks guidelines on time factors affecting robot use (4.3.1.)	Update the standard with design measures and guidelines to ensure a safe spiral of adaptation.
	Sections 5.1 6.9	ISO 13482:2014 provides insufficient guidance on transparent HRI (4.3.2)	Update the standard with design measures to ensure that the robot's intentions are transparent to users and third parties.

Figure 2. (continued).

specific robot types. As a result, robots may end up harming users in very unexpected ways [50,117]. Our distinctive contribution lies precisely in a focused examination of the ISO 13482:2014 standard's deficiencies

within a specific category of robots, such as lower-limb exoskeletons, that are closely integrated with the human body, and how this unique characteristic and its accompanying challenges have been overlooked

	Section 5.10.8	ISO 13482:2014 does not have safety requirements regarding third parties (non-users) that might enter into contact with the robot (4.3.3)	Update the standard with design measures to ensure that third parties (e.g., bystanders) interact with the robot safely and are protected from any harm caused by the robot in such interaction.
DEFINITION OF SAFEGUARD MEASURES	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	---	ISO 13482:2014 does not provide guidance on how to respond once a fall occurs or is unavoidable (4.4.1.)	Update the standard with safeguard measures for scenarios where falls are unavoidable or have occurred.
	---	ISO 13482:2014 does not include instructions on how to address residual software faults (4.4.2)	Update the standard with safeguard measures to correct software faults.
	---	The regulation by domain-safety functions is unsuitable in some scenarios (4.4.3)	Assign the main robot controller to a high integrity level (depending on a risk assessment).
	Section 6.2	ISO 13482:2014's lacks guidance on protective stops (4.4.4)	Determine scenarios where it is safe to activate protective and emergency stops. The button triggering a protective stop should be easily reachable for the user. Exoskeleton should not power down if a protective stop is triggered in certain scenarios. Add requirements for graceful collapsing.
	---	ISO 13482:2014 does not cover the robots full life cycle (4.4.5)	Update the standard with safeguard measures for the full life cycle (e.g., remanufacturing, recycling, disposal) to the standard.

Figure 2. (continued).

within the broader standardization framework.

As it happens with food, pharmaceuticals, or chemicals, tailoring safety measures for distinct robot categories and embodiments is

essential to meet an adequate level of safety. However, balancing comprehensive guidelines with practical feasibility for all covered personal care robot types may be challenging due to inherent variations and

INFORMATION FOR USE	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	Section 8	ISO 13482:2014 does not provide guidance on information for use concerning different users and third parties like family members or trainers (4.5.1.)	Update the standard with requirements for information for different people who might interact with the robot.
VERIFICATION AND VALIDATION METHODS	SECTION	AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	RECOMMENDATION
	Section 7	There is a lack of verification and validation methods, and there are no commonly agreed physiological measurements to provide data about the effects of long term use of exoskeletons (4.6.1)	Update the standard with performance standards and test methods procedures for exoskeletons, including physiological measurement about the effects of long-term use. Include requirements on data collection and analysis to be used as a basis for understanding long-term effects.
	Section 4	There is a lack of HRI models (4.6.2)	Update the standard with a conceptual model to forecast the implications of close HRI.

Figure 2. (continued).

complexities. Still, technological complexity, difficulty, and variety should never be a justification to refrain from creating safety standards that provide safeguards to ensure the robot’s operation. To that end, recent projects such as the European Research Council (ERC) Starting Grant Safe and Sound⁵ uses robot testbeds, open data, the interaction between regulators and developers, and active patient engagement to support regulators’ proactive, engaged role in effectively addressing unique nuances and safety concerns across different personal care robot categories. Ultimately, this could mean that a standard for each robot category enhancing safety and usability universally across more equal robot devices (e.g., among physical assistant robots or social robots only) would perhaps frame the related safety issues more evenly. Failing to do so will inevitably entail robot developers overlooking essential legal considerations into their designs, with the consequent development of systems that can cause harm to users [15,16]. Then, the literature will continue to highlight how these robots raise ethical, legal, and societal aspects [118,119].

Our most pivotal message, without a doubt, revolves around the shared responsibility that all stakeholders within the personal care robot ecosystem [35,120] should embrace. In this pursuit, it becomes

⁵ See ERC Starting Grant SAFE and SOUND, available at <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/research/research-projects/law/safe-sound-towards-evidence-based-policies-for-safe-and-sound-robots>.

imperative for this concerted endeavor to encompass all the relevant stakeholders and beyond, each contributing their expertise and commitment to ensure the comprehensive enhancement of safety and functionality across all facets of personal care robot technology. In this respect, although developers undoubtedly need to strive to integrate these dimensions into their designs, it is also true that standards could improve so they do a better job guiding technology developments. It is time to learn from these lessons and improve ISO 13482:2014 [89]; Drukarch, Calleja, & Fosch-Villaronga, 2022) so we can make the standard fit for a world where activities like walking or going to a meeting will increasingly depend on the assistance of robots assembled to our bodies.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eduard Fosch-Villaronga: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Carlos José Calleja:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Hadassah Drukarch:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Diego Torricelli:** Writing – review & editing.

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There has been no use of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.

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References

- [1] D. Greenbaum, Ethical, legal and social concerns relating to exoskeletons, *Comput. Soc. 45* (3) (2016) 234–239.
- [2] A. Kapeller, H. Felzmann, E. Fosch Villaronga, K. Nizamis, A. Hughes, Implementing ethical, legal, and societal considerations in wearable robot design, *Appl. Sci. 11* (15) (2021) 6705.
- [3] E. Fosch-Villaronga, Legal frame of non-social personal care robots, *New Trends Med Service Robot. 48* (2017) 229–242.
- [4] EURO-BENCH Robotics, Why address ethical, legal and social issues with wearable robots early on? [Video]. YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nFzARVsXLV8>, 2021. (Accessed 18 February 2022).
- [5] A. Kapeller, H. Felzmann, E. Fosch-Villaronga, A. Hughes, A taxonomy of ethical, legal and social implications of wearable robots: an expert perspective, *Sci. Eng. Ethics 26* (6) (2020) 3229–3247.
- [6] D. Torricelli, J. Pons, EURO-BENCH: preparing robots for the real world, in: *Biosystems & Biorobotics, Wearable Robotics: Challenges and Trends*, vol. 22, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018, pp. 375–378.
- [7] E. Fosch-Villaronga, *Robots, Healthcare and the Law: Regulating Automation in Personal Healthcare*, Routledge, London, 2019.
- [8] P. Salvini, D. Paez-Granados, A. Billard, On the Safety of Mobile Robots Serving in Public Spaces: identifying gaps in an ISO 13482:2014 and calling for a new standard, *ACM Transactions on Human-Robotic Interaction 10* (3) (2021) 1–27.
- [9] Z. Dolic, R. Castro, A. Moarcas, Robots in Healthcare: a Solution or a Problem?, Study for the Committee on Environment, Public Health, and Food Safety, Retrieved from, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, European Parliament, Luxembourg, 2019, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2019/638391/IPOL_IDA\(2019\)638391_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2019/638391/IPOL_IDA(2019)638391_EN.pdf).
- [10] D. Simshaw, N. Terry, K. Hauser, M.L. Cummings, Regulating healthcare robots: maximizing opportunities while minimizing risks, *Rich. KL & Tech. 22* (2015) 1.
- [11] E. Gómez-González, E. Gómez, Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Healthcare: Applications, Availability and Societal Impact, EUR 30197 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2760/047666>. https://idus.us.es/bitstream/handle/11441/105744/jrc120214_ai_in_medicine_and_healthcare_report-aiwatch_v50.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y.
- [12] E. Fosch-Villaronga, A. Cartolovni, R.L. Pierce, Promoting inclusiveness in exoskeleton robotics: addressing challenges for pediatric access, *Paladyn. J. Behav. Rob. 11* (1) (2020) 327–339.
- [13] R. Soraa, Mechanical genders: how do humans gender robots? *Gend. Technol. Dev. 21* (1–2) (2017) 99–115.
- [14] J. Boada, B. Maestre, C. Genís, The ethical issues of social assistive robotics: a critical literature review, *Technol. Soc. 67* (2021), 101726.
- [15] E. Fosch-Villaronga, T. Mahler, Cybersecurity, safety and robots: strengthening the link between cybersecurity and safety in the context of care robots, *Comput. Law Secur. Rep. 41* (2021), 105528.
- [16] A. Martinetti, P. Chemweno, K. Nizamis, E. Fosch Villaronga, Redefining safety in light of human-robot interaction: a critical review of current standards and regulations, *Frontiers in chemical engineering*, 2021-07-27, Vol.3, *Front. Chem. Eng. 3* (2021).
- [17] B. Eysenbach, S. Gu, J. Ibarz, S. Levine, Leave No Trace: Learning to Reset for Safe and Autonomous Reinforcement Learning, arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.06782, 2017.
- [18] T. Vandemeulebroucke, B.D. de Casterlé, C. Gastmans, Ethics of socially assistive robots in aged-care settings: a socio-historical contextualisation, *J. Med. Ethics 46* (2) (2020) 128–136.
- [19] H.S. Satra, The foundations of a policy for the use of social robots in care, *Technol. Soc. 63* (2020), 101383.
- [20] D.B.O. Boesl, T. Haidegger, A. Khamis, V. Mai, C. Mörch, B. Rao, A. Jacobs, B. Vanderborcht, Automating the achievement of SDGs: robotics enabling & inhibiting the accomplishment of the SDGs, Retrieved from, in: *The United Nations Interagency Task Team on Science, Technology and Innovation for the SDGs (IATT), Report for the Multi-Stakeholder Forum on Science, Technology and Innovation 2021: Emerging Science, Frontier Technologies, and the SDGs: Perspectives from the UN System and Science and Technology Communities*, 2021, pp. 120–126 <https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/IATT%20report%20on%20emerging%20techs%202021.pdf>. (Accessed 4 September 2023).
- [21] J. Reis, N. Melão, J. Salvadorinho, B. Soares, A. Rosete, Service robots in the hospitality industry: the case of Henn-na hotel, Japan, *Technol. Soc. 63* (2020), 101423.
- [22] E. Fosch-Villaronga, G.S. Virk, Legal issues for mobile servant robots, in: A. Rodić, T. Borangiu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 25th Conference on Robotics Alpe-Adria-Danube Region. Advances in Robot Design and Intelligent Control*, vol. 2016, Springer, 2016, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49058-8_66.
- [23] B.D. Lowe, W.G. Billotte, D.R. Peterson, ASTM F48 formation and standards for industrial exoskeletons and exosuits, *IIEE transactions on occupational ergonomics and human factors 7* (3–4) (2019) 230–236.
- [24] ASTM International, F3358-18 - Standard Practice for Labeling and Information for Exoskeletons, Retrieved from, ASTM International, 2018, <https://www.astm.org/f3358-18.html>. (Accessed 4 September 2023).
- [25] ASTM International, F3323-19 - Standard Terminology for Exoskeletons and Exosuits, Retrieved from, ASTM International, 2019, <https://www.astm.org/f3323-19.html>. (Accessed 4 September 2023).
- [26] ASTM International, F3427 - Standard Practice for Documenting Environmental Conditions for Utilization with Exoskeleton Test Methods, Retrieved from, ASTM International, 2020, <https://www.astm.org/f3427-20.html>. (Accessed 4 September 2023).
- [27] C 220, Communication in the Framework of the Implementation of the Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 on Machinery, and Amending Directive 95/16/EC (Recast). European Commission, Official Journal of the European Union, July 2014, p. 11, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:2014:220:FULL&from=EN>.
- [28] H. Drukarch, C. Calleja, E. Fosch-Villaronga, e8, *An Iterative Regulatory Process for Robot Governance. Data & Policy*, vol. 5, Cambridge University Press, 2023, pp. 1–22.
- [29] M.J. Page, J.E. McKenzie, P.M. Bossuyt, I. Boutron, D. Moher, The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews, *BMJ n71* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
- [30] D. Moher, A. Liberati, J. Tetzlaff, D.G. Altman, Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and metaanalyses: the PRISMA statement, *Ann. Intern. Med. 151* (2009) 264–269.
- [31] E. Cole, New international standards boon to personal care robotics: new ISO standards open personal care robotics to mainstream adoption, *Robot. Bus. Rev.* (2014). Retrieved from https://www.roboticsbusinessreview.com/legal/new_international_standards_boon_to_personal_care_robotics/.
- [32] E. Fosch-Villaronga, ISO 13482:2014 and its confusing categories. Building a bridge between law and robotics, *New Trends Med Service Robot. 39* (2016) 31–44.
- [33] M.P. Lawton, E.M. Brody, Assessment of older people: self-maintaining and instrumental activities of daily living, *Gerontol. 9* (3) (1969) 179–186.
- [34] Dictionary Collins, Definition of Personal Care, retrieved from, 2019, <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/personal-care>.
- [35] E. Fosch-Villaronga, H. Drukarch, On Healthcare Robots: Concepts, Definitions, and Considerations for Healthcare Robot Governance, ArXiv pre-print, 2021, pp. 1–87.
- [36] International Organization for Standardization, Robots and robotic devices — safety requirements for industrial robots — Part 2: robot systems and integration (ISO 10218-2:2011), Retrieved from, <https://www.iso.org/standard/41571.html>, 2011. (Accessed 6 December 2021).
- [37] International Organization for Standardization, Robots and robotic devices — safety requirements for industrial robots — Part 1: robots (ISO 10218-1:2011), Retrieved from, <https://www.iso.org/standard/51330.html>, 2011. (Accessed 6 December 2021).
- [38] E. Fosch-Villaronga, in: P. Cunningham, M. Cunningham (Eds.), *Legal and Regulatory Challenges for Physical Assistant Robots*, vol. 2015, IEEE IMC International Information Management Corporation, 2015, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/eCHALLENGES.2015.7441057>.
- [39] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 8373:2021 Robotics — Vocabulary, 2021. <https://www.iso.org/standard/75539.html>. (Accessed 7 September 2023).
- [40] T. Zielinska, History of service robots, in: M. Ceccarelli (Ed.), *Service Robots and Robotics: Design and Application*, IGI Global, Hershey, 2012, pp. 1–14.

- [41] IEEE Standards Association, IEEE 1872-2015 - IEEE Standard Ontologies for Robotics and Automation, 2015. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7084073>. (Accessed 7 September 2023).
- [42] M. Valori, A. Scibilia, I. Fassi, J. Saenz, R. Behrens, S. Herbster, K. Nielsen, Validating safety in human–robot collaboration: standards and new perspectives, *Robotics* 10 (2) (2021) 65.
- [43] E. Fosch-Villaronga, H. Drukarch, LIAISON D1.1 Report on Safety Standards Uncovered Challenges, Persistent URL, Retrieved from eLaw - Center for Law and Digital Technologies, Leiden University, 2021 <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/3204017>.
- [44] E. Fosch-Villaronga, B. Özcan, The progressive intertwinement between design, human needs and the regulation of care technology: the case of lower-limb exoskeletons, *Int. J.Soci. Robot.* 12 (4) (2019) 959–972.
- [45] A. Poulsen, E. Fosch-Villaronga, R. Søraa, Queering machines, *Nat. Mach. Intell.* 2 (3) (2020) 152.
- [46] E. Fosch-Villaronga, H. Drukarch, Accounting for diversity in robot design, testbeds, and safety standardization, *Int. J.Soci. Robot.* 1–19 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-023-00974-6>.
- [47] W. Barfield, A. Williams, Cyborgs and enhancement technology, *Philosophie* 2 (4) (2017) 4.
- [48] J.S. Breen, The exoskeleton generation—disability redux, *Disabil. Soc.* 30 (10) (2015) 1568–1572.
- [49] E. Palmerini, F. Azzarri, F. Battaglia, A. Bertolini, A. Carnevale, J. Carpaneto, et al., Regulating Emerging Robotic Technologies in Europe: Robotics Facing Law and Ethics, 2014.
- [50] D. Amodei, C. Olah, J. Steinhart, P. Christiano, J. Schulman, D. Mané, Concrete Problems in AI Safety, arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.06565, 2016.
- [51] E. Fosch-Villaronga, A. Golia Jr., Robots, Standards and the Law. Rivalries between private standards and public policymaking for robot governance, *Comput. Law Secur. Rep.* 35 (2) (2019) 129–144.
- [52] L. Schiebinger, Scientific research must take gender into account, *Nature* 507 (2014) 9, <https://doi.org/10.1038/507009a>.
- [53] Nature Editorial, Science benefits from diversity, *Nature* 558 (2018) 5–6. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05326-3>.
- [54] C. Tannenbaum, R.P. Ellis, F. Eysse, J. Zou, L. Schiebinger, Sex and gender analysis improves science and engineering, *Nature* 575 (7781) (2019) 137–146.
- [55] D. Cirillo, S. Catuara-Solarz, C. Morey, E. Guney, L. Subirats, S. Mellino, N. Mavridis, Sex and gender differences and biases in artificial intelligence for biomedicine and healthcare, *NPJ Digit. Med.* 3 (1) (2020) 1–11.
- [56] E. Fosch-Villaronga, P. Khanna, H. Drukarch, B.H.M. Custers, The Role of Humans in Surgery Automation. Exploring the Influence of Automation on Human-Robot Interaction and Responsibility in Surgery Innovation. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, forthcoming, 2022.
- [57] T. Jacobs, G.S. Virk, (2014) ISO 13482 - the New Safety Standard for Personal Care Robots, in: 41st International Symposium on Robotics, vol. 2014, ISR/ Robotik, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [58] P. Caleb-Solly, C. Harper, S. Dogramadzi, Standards and regulations for physically assistive robots, in: IEEE International Conference on Intelligence and Safety for Robotics (ISR), 2021, 2021, pp. 259–263.
- [59] J. Tamez-Duque, R. Cobian-Ugalde, A. Kilicarslan, A. Venkatakrishnan, R. Soto, J. L. Contreras-Vidal, Real-time strap pressure sensor system for powered exoskeletons, *Sensors* 15 (2) (2015) 4550–4563.
- [60] K. Langlois, D. Rodriguez-Cianca, B. Serrien, J. De Winter, T. Verstraten, C. Rodriguez-Guerrero, et al., Investigating the effects of strapping pressure on human-robot interface dynamics using a soft robotic cuff, 1, *IEEE Trans Med Robot Bionics* 3202 (2020) 1.
- [61] M. Marks, Robots in Space: Sharing the Sidewalk with Autonomous Delivery Vehicles, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3347466>.
- [62] K. Thomsen, Robots, regulation, and the changing nature of public space, *Ottawa Law Rev.* 51 (2) (2019) 275.
- [63] R.L. Pierce, E. Fosch-Villaronga, Available at, in: M. Ienca, et al. (Eds.), *Medical Robotics and the Right to Health Care: A Progressive Realisation*, vol. 2022, Cambridge Handbook of Life Science, Information Technology and Human Rights, forthcoming, 2022. : https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3809591.
- [64] C.D. Murray, J. Fox, Body image and prosthesis satisfaction in the lower limb amputee, *Disabil. Rehabil.* 24 (17) (2002) 925–931.
- [65] L. Bissolotti, F. Nicoli, M. Picozzi, Domestic use of the exoskeleton for gait training in patients with spinal cord injuries: ethical dilemmas in clinical practice, *Front. Neurosci.* 12 (FEB) (2018) 1–5.
- [66] D. Greenbaum, Ethical, legal and social concerns relating to exoskeletons, *Comput. Soc.* 45 (3) (2015) 234–239.
- [67] E. Fosch-Villaronga, Towards a Legal and Ethical Framework for Personal Care Robots. Analysis of Person Carrier, Physical Assistant and Mobile Servant Robots, Doctoral Dissertation., Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27829.17127>.
- [68] British Standards Institution, Robots and Robotic Devices. Guide to the Ethical Design and Application of Robots and Robotic Systems (BS 8611:2016), Retrieved from: 2016 <https://shop.bsigroup.com/products/robots-and-robotic-devices-guide-to-the-ethical-design-and-application-of-robots-and-robotic-systems/standard>. (Accessed 20 January 2022).
- [69] A.M. Aroyo, J. De Bruyne, O. Dheu, E. Fosch-Villaronga, A. Gudkov, H. Hoch, A. Tamò-Larriex, Overtrusting robots: setting a research agenda to mitigate overtrust in automation, *Paladyn. J. Behav. Rob.* 12 (1) (2021) 423–436.
- [70] H. Felzmann, E.F. Villaronga, C. Lutz, A. Tamò-Larriex, Transparency you can trust: transparency requirements for artificial intelligence between legal norms and contextual concerns, *Big Data Soc.* 6 (1) (2019), 2053951719860542.
- [71] S.C. Robinson, Trust, transparency, and openness: how inclusion of cultural values shapes Nordic national public policy strategies for artificial intelligence (AI), *Technol. Soc.* 63 (2020), 101421.
- [72] D. Meyerson, K.E. Weick, R.M. Kramer, Swift trust and temporary groups, *Trust Organ.: Front. Theor. Res.* 166 (1996) 195.
- [73] K. Blomqvist, K. Cook, Swift trust, in: *The Routledge Companion to Trust*, first ed., Vol. 1, Routledge, 2018, pp. 29–49.
- [74] J.D. Lee, K.A. See, Trust in automation: designing for appropriate reliance, *Hum. Factors* 46 (1) (2004) 50–80.
- [75] P. Hancock, D. Billings, K. Schaefer, J. Chen, E. De Visser, R. Parasuraman, A meta-analysis of factors affecting trust in human-robot interaction, *Hum. Factors* 53 (5) (2011) 517–527.
- [76] H.S. Sætra, Social robot deception and the culture of trust, *Paladyn. J. Behav. Rob.* 12 (1) (2021) 276–286.
- [77] E.E. Levine, M.E. Schweitzer, Prosocial lies: when deception breeds trust, *Organ. Behav. Hum. Decis. Process.* 126 (2015) 88–106.
- [78] M. Salem, G. Lakatos, F. Amirabdollahian, K. Dautenhahn, Towards safe and trustworthy social robots: ethical challenges and practical issues, in: *Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Social Robotics*, vol. 9388, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2015, pp. 584–593.
- [79] R. Van den Brule, R. Dotsch, G. Bijlstra, D. Wigboldus, P. Haselager, Do robot performance and behavioral style affect human trust? *Int. J.Soci. Robot.* 6 (4) (2014) 519–531.
- [80] K. Delbaere, G. Crombez, G. Vanderstraeten, T. Willems, D. Cambier, Fear-related avoidance of activities falls and physical frailty. A prospective community-based cohort study, *Age Ageing* 33 (4) (2004) 368–373.
- [81] R. Cumming, G. Salkeld, M. Thomas, G. Szonyi, Prospective study of the impact of fear of falling on activities of daily living, SF-36 scores, and nursing home admission, *J. Gerontol. Series A, Biol. Sci. Med. Sci.* 55 (5) (2000) M299–M305.
- [82] M. Salem, G. Lakatos, F. Amirabdollahian, K. Dautenhahn, Would you trust a (faulty) robot?, in: *Proceedings of the Tenth Annual ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-robot Interaction*, 2015, 2015, pp. 141–148.
- [83] N. Umeda, H. Ishihara, T. Ikeda, M. Asada, The first impressions of small humanoid robots modulate the process of how touch affects personality what they are, *Adv. Robot.* (2021) 1–13.
- [84] J. Parviainen, T. Turja, L. Van Aerscht, Robots and human touch in care: desirable and non-desirable robot assistance, *Soc. Robot.* 11357 (2018) 533–540.
- [85] J. Wright, Tactile care, mechanical Hugs: Japanese caregivers and robotic lifting devices, *Asian Anthropol.* 17 (1) (2018) 24–39.
- [86] E. Fosch-Villaronga, C. Millard, Cloud robotics law and regulation: challenges in the governance of complex and dynamic cyber-physical ecosystems, *Robot. Autonom. Syst.* 119 (2019) 77–91.
- [87] D. Quarta, M. Pogliani, M. Polino, F. Maggi, A.M. Zanchettin, S. Zanero, An experimental security analysis of an industrial robot controller, in: *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, vol. 2017, SP), 2017, pp. 268–286.
- [88] D. Kim, M. Roh, J.S. Lee, B. Seo, S. Jeoung, Proposal on determination of protective stop space of mobile servant robots for ISO13482. 17th International Conference on Control, Automat. Syst. (ICCAS) (2017) 608–613.
- [89] C. Calleja, H. Drukarch, E. Fosch-Villaronga, Harnessing robot experimentation to optimise the regulatory framing of emerging robot technologies, Sept 14-16, 2021, in: *Accepted for Presentation at the Data for Policy 2021 Conference*, 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/5211110#.YRtaZS0RoV>.
- [90] K. Akdemir, D. Karakoyunlu, T. Padir, B. Sunar, An emerging threat: eve meets a robot (work-in-progress), *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.* 6802 (2011) 271–289.
- [91] E. Fosch-Villaronga, H. Felzmann, M. Ramos-Montero, T. Mahler, Cloud services for robotic nurses? Assessing legal and ethical issues in the use of cloud services for healthcare robots, in: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, vol. 2018, 2018, pp. 290–296.
- [92] F.J.R. Lera, C.F. Llamas, Á.M. Guerrero, V.M. Olivera, Cybersecurity of robotics and autonomous systems: privacy and safety, in: G. Dekoulis (Ed.), *Robotics: Legal, Ethical and Socioeconomic Impacts*. IntechOpen, 2017. <https://cdn.intechopen.com/pdfs/56025.pdf>.
- [93] T. Bonaci, J. Herron, T. Yusuf, J. Yan, T. Kohno, H.J. Chizeck, To Make a Robot Secure: an Experimental Analysis of Cyber Security Threats against Teleoperated Surgical Robots, arXiv, 2015, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1504.04339>.
- [94] G.W. Clark, M.V. Doran, T.R. Andel, Cybersecurity issues in robotics, in: *2017 IEEE Conference on Cognitive and Computational Aspects of Situation Management*, vols. 1–5, CogSIMA), 2017.
- [95] E.R. Vieira, R.C. Palmer, P.H. Chaves, Prevention of falls in older people living in the community, *BMJ* 353 (2016) 1–13.
- [96] A. Yesim, Y. Ulus, T. Berna, L. Tomak, Y. Zahiroglu, A. Bilgili, O. Kuru, AB0353 Associated factors for falls and fear of falling in ambulatory patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a comparative study with healthy subjects, *Ann. Rheum. Dis.* 76 (Suppl 2) (2017) 1172.
- [97] L. Yardley, N. Beyer, K. Hauer, G. Kempen, C. Piot-Ziegler, C. Todd, Development and initial validation of the falls efficacy scale-international (FES-I), *Age Ageing* 34 (6) (2005) 614–619.
- [98] J. Guiochet, M. Machin, H. Waeselynyck, Safety-critical advanced robots: a survey, *Robot. Autonom. Syst.* 94 (2017) 43–52.
- [99] A. Remazeilles, A. Dominguez, P. Barralon, A. Torres-Pardo, D. Pinto, F. Aller, D. Torricelli, Making bipedal robot experiments reproducible and comparable: the Eurobench software approach, *Front. Robot. and AI* 9 (2022), 951663.

- [100] H. Herr, A. Wilkenfeld, User-adaptive control of a magnetorheological prosthetic knee, *Ind. Robot. Int. J.* 30 (2003) 42–55.
- [101] D. Crestani, K. Godary-Dejean, L. Lapiere, Enhancing fault tolerance of autonomous mobile robots, *Robot. Autom. Syst.* 68 (2015) 140–155.
- [102] M. Doran, R. Sterritt, G. Wilkie, Autonomic architecture for fault handling in mobile robots, *Innovat. Syst. Software Eng.* 16 (3) (2020) 263–288.
- [103] J.R. Ward, P.J. Clarkson, An analysis of medical device-related errors: prevalence and possible solutions, *J. Med. Eng. Technol.* 28 (1) (2004) 2–6.
- [104] S. Courdier, O. Garbin, M. Hummel, V. Thoma, E. Ball, R. Favre, A. Wattiez, Equipment failure: causes and consequences in endoscopic gynecologic surgery, *J. Minim. Invasive Gynecol.* 16 (1) (2009) 28–33.
- [105] S. Hempel, M. Maggard-Gibbons, D.K. Nguyen, A.J. Dawes, I. Miale-Lye, J. M. Beroes, P.G. Shekelle, Wrong-site surgery, retained surgical items, and surgical fires: a systematic review of surgical never events, *JAMA surgery* 150 (8) (2015) 796–805.
- [106] N. Garmann-Johnsen, T. Mettler, M. Sprenger, Service Robotics in Healthcare: a Perspective for Information Systems Researchers?, Retrieved from, 2014, https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Tobias-Mettler/publication/267763443_Service_Robotics_in_Healthcare_A_Perspective_for_Information_Systems_Researchers/links/545a0a2f0cf2bccc4912fca5/Service-Robotics-in-Healthcare-A-Perspective-for-Information-Systems-Researchers.pdf.
- [107] R. Bostelman, T. Hong, Test Methods for Exoskeletons—Lessons Learned from Industrial and Response Robotics, 2018.
- [108] H. Felzmann, E. Fosch-Villaronga, C. Lutz, A. Tamo-Larrieux, Robots and transparency: the multiple dimensions of transparency in the context of robot technologies, *IEEE Robot. Autom. Mag.* 26 (2) (2019) 71–78.
- [109] Q. Chen, H. Cheng, C. Yue, R. Huang, H. Guo, Dynamic Balance Gait for Walking Assistance Exoskeleton, vol. 2018, *Applied bionics and biomechanics*, 2018.
- [110] P. Barattini, A practical appraisal of ISO 13482 as a reference for an orphan robot category, in: P. Barattini, F. Vicentini, G. Singh Virk, t. Haidegger (Eds.), *Human-Robot Interaction Safety, Standardization, and Benchmarking* (103-121), CRC Press/Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, 2019.
- [111] J. Veneman, Safety standardization of wearable robots—the need for testing methods, in: *Biosystems & Biorobotics, Wearable Robotics: Challenges and Trends*, vol. 16, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016, pp. 189–193.
- [112] S. Massardi, D. Pinto-Fernandez, J. Babić, M. Dezman, A. Trošt, V. Grosu, D. Lefeber, C. Rodriguez, J. Bessler, L. Schaake, G. Prange-Lasonder, J. F. Veneman, D. Torricelli, Relevance of hazards in exoskeleton applications: a survey-based enquiry, *J. NeuroEng. Rehabil.* 20 (1) (2023 May 31) 68.
- [113] J. Bessler, G.B. Prange-Lasonder, L. Schaake, J.F. Saenz, C. Bidard, I. Fassi, M. Valori, A.B. Lassen, J.H. Buurke, Safety assessment of rehabilitation robots: a review identifying safety skills and current knowledge gaps, *Front. Robot. and AI* 8 (2021), 602878, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2021.602878>.
- [114] International Organization for Standardization, Robotics — application of ISO 13482 — Part 1: safety-related test methods (ISO/TR 23482-1:2020), Retrieved from, <https://www.iso.org/standard/71564.html>, 2020. (Accessed 6 December 2021).
- [115] International Electrotechnical Commission, Medical electrical equipment — Part 2-78: particular requirements for basic safety and essential performance of medical robots for rehabilitation, assessment, compensation or alleviation (IEC 80601-2-78:2019), Retrieved from, <https://www.iso.org/standard/68474.html>, 2019. (Accessed 6 December 2021).
- [116] B. Rupal, S. Rafique, A. Singla, E. Singla, M. Isaksson, G. Virk, Lower-limb exoskeletons, *Int. J. Adv. Rob. Syst.* 14 (6) (2017), 172988141774355.
- [117] G.E. Yu, S.T. Hong, K.Y. Sung, J.H. Seo, A study on the risk investigation and safety of personal care robots, in: 2017 17th International Conference on Control, Automation and Systems (ICCAS), IEEE, 2017, October, pp. 904–908.
- [118] A. van Wynsberghe, *Healthcare Robots: Ethics, Design and Implementation*, Routledge, 2016.
- [119] C. Holder, V. Khurana, F. Harrison, L. Jacobs, Robotics and law: key legal and regulatory implications of the robotics age (Part I of II), *Comput. Law Secur. Rep.* 32 (3) (2016) 383–402.
- [120] L.D. Riek, Healthcare robotics, *Commun. ACM* 60 (11) (2017) 68–78.

Eduard Fosch-Villaronga Ph.D. LL.M M.A. is Associate Professor and Director of Research at the eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies at Leiden University (NL). Eduard is an ERC Laureate and investigates the legal and regulatory aspects of robot and AI technologies, with a special focus on healthcare, governance, diversity, and privacy. Eduard Fosch-Villaronga is the Principal Investigator (PI) of his ERC Starting Grant SAFE & SOUND: Towards Evidence-based Policies for Safe and Sound Robot. Eduard is also the PI of eLaw’s contribution to the Horizon Europe BIAS: Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labour Market and visiting scholar at Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC), where he explores the use of AI for preventing diabetic foot syndrome at the vascular surgery department. Eduard Fosch-Villaronga was assistant professor at eLaw during 2021-2022. During this time, Eduard was the Principal Investigator of PROPELLING (2021-2022), an FSTP from the H2020 Eurobench project, a project using robot testing zones to support evidence-based robot policies. He is also the co-leader of the Gendering Algorithms project, an interdisciplinary pilot project aiming to explore the functioning, effects, and governance policies of AI-based gender classification systems. In 2021, he was the PI of LIAISON, an FSTP from the H2020 COVR project that aims to link robot development and policymaking to reduce the complexity of robot legal compliance. Eduard was also the co-leader of the Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects Working Group at the H2020 Cost Action 16116 on Wearable Robots and currently participates actively in the Social Responsibility Working Group at the H2020 Cost Action 19121 GoodBrother. In 2020 and 2022, Eduard served the European Commission in the Sub-Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI), connected products, and other new challenges in product safety to the Consumer Safety Network (CSN) to revise the General Product Safety Directive. Eduard holds an Erasmus Mundus Joint Doctorate in Law, Science, & Technology, coordinated by the University of Bologna (2017), an LL.M. from the University of Toulouse (2012), an M.A. from the Autonomous University of Madrid (2013), and an LL.B. from the Autonomous University of Barcelona (2011).

Carlos Calleja is a Research Assistant at the eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies at Leiden University. He investigates the legal and regulatory aspects of robot and AI technologies, focusing on wearable robots and verification and validation methods. Previously, he was part of the Vulnerabilities in the Robot Society (VIROS) project at the University of Oslo. Carlos holds an LL.B from the Catholic University Andres Bello (2015) and an M.Phil from the University of Oslo (2021).

Hadassah Drukarch is a Researcher at the eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies at Leiden University. She focuses on law, digital technologies, governance, corporate law, healthcare robots, and responsibility. Hadassah is also the founder and host of The Law of Tech Podcast, which provides insights into how new technologies impact the law and legal industry. Previously, Hadassah worked on LIAISON, an FSTP from the H2020 COVR project linking robot development and policymaking to reduce the complexity in robot legal compliance. She holds an LL.B. in International Business Law and an Honours College Law Program certificate from Leiden University.

Diego Torricelli received a MSc degree in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Roma TRE (2004). His Master’s thesis was developed in Harvard Medical School, Boston, in the Gait Analysis Lab of the Spaulding Rehab Hospital. In 2009 he received the PhD in Biomedical Engineering from University of Roma TRE, with a thesis focused on eye-driven interfaces for rehabilitation. In 2008 he co-founded a spin-off company for the development of innovative human-computer interfaces. He is now working at the Bioengineering Group of CSIC in Madrid, focusing on the study of human motor control principles and their application to technology-based neurorehabilitation.